

Two-winged insects (Insecta: Diptera) of Pirin

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Abstract: A total of 742 two-winged species that belong to 43 families have been reported from Pirin Mt. The larger number of species (394 species, or 53.2%) has been found in the beech forest belt. The established species belong to 72 areo-geographical categories. The dipterous fauna can be divided into 2 main groups: 1) species with Mediterranean type of distribution (48 species, or 6.4%) – more thermophilic and distributed mainly in the southern parts of the Palaearctic. Five species of southern type, distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it, can be formally related to this group as well; 2) species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (694 species, or 93.6%) – more cold-resistant and widely distributed in the Palaearctic. 155 species of northern type, distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it, can be formally related to this group as well. The zoogeographical character of the Tachinidae fauna is determined by the second group. The ration of the two groups is different in the separate vegetation belts of Pirin Mt.

Key words: Diptera, Bulgaria, Pirin Mt., faunistic composition

Introduction

The first data for Diptera of Pirin Mt. are reported by DRENSKY (1929). Between the two world wars DRENSKY (1934, 1939, 1943), VALKANOV (1941) and DELKESKAMP (1942) published separate data about the mountain. In the next period of 14 years there are no works concerning dipterans of Pirin Mt. After 1956, articles including materials from the mountain, reappear (DRENSKY, 1957; GREGOR & POVOLNY, 1959; NAIDENOV, 1962; DUŠEK & ROZKOŠNY, 1963; HRADSKY & MOUCHA, 1964, 1967; LAVČIEV, 1964, 1980, 2003; BANKOWSKA, 1967a, 1967b; BESHOVSKI, 1967, 1976, 1978, 1980, 1982, 1984, 1994, 1995, 1998, 2004, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2013; BERON, 1972; CHVÁLA et al., 1972; STARÝ, 1973, 1976, 1978; KOVATCHEV, 1976; SPITZER, 1978; BEIGER, 1979; CHVÁLA, 1980; HUBENOV, 1980, 1982a, 1982b, 1983; JOOST, 1982; ROZKOŠNY, 1982; LAUTERER, 1983; PARVU, 1983; KRZEMIŃSKI, 1984; MENDEL, 1986; CHVÁLA & KOVALEV, 1989; KRZEMIŃSKI & STARÝ, 1989; MICHAILOVA, 1989; POVOLNÝ & VERVES, 1990; BECHEV, 1991, 1994, 2001, 2004, 2006, 2010; BESHOVSKI & MINKOVA, 1991; SKUHRAVA et al., 1991; BESHOVSKI, MANASIEVA, 1995; BESHOVSKI & DZHAMBASOV, 1997, 1998, 2002; GANEVA, 1998; BESHOVSKI & ZATWARNICKI, 2000, 2001a, 2001b,

2002, 2004; DZHAMBASOV & BESHOVSKI, 2000; LANGOUROV, 2001; ČERNI & MERZ, 2006). The hydrobiological (VALKANOV, 1941; STOICHEV, 1996) and biospeleological (BERON, 2006) studies have a faunistic contribution.

The data are fragmentary, concern separated parts of the mountain and are scattered in different articles which are not specially referred to Pirin Mt. There are systematic studies of the explored territory only for the family Tachinidae (HUBENOV, 1992). There is a lack of generalized investigations on the tachinid fauna of the mountain. In the management plan for Pirin National Park, unlike the other two national parks (Central Balkan and Rila), the dipterans are not considered.

The aim of this paper is to present information concerning the fauna, zoogeography and study level of the two-winged insects of Pirin Mt. and Pirin National Park.

Investigated region, materials and methods

Pirin Mt. is situated between the valleys of the rivers Srtuma and Mesta, south of Rila Mt., from

which it is separated by Predel Col. The Paril Col separates Pirin Mt. from the south situated Slavyanka Mt. Pirin Mt. stretches northwest-southeast and is about 80 km long and 40 km wide. The maximum height at Vihren Peak is 2914.3 m. The total area of the mountain is 2585 km². It is divided into North, Middle and South Pirin. In the Pleistocene glacial forms (carlings, cirques, trog valleys and moraines) are formed in Pirin Mt. Gravity forms of alpine type (scree, stone rivers and seas, snowslide cones, gullies and moraine shafts) are characteristic of its high parts. Climatically Pirin Mt. belongs to Continental-Mediterranean climatic region and includes parts of the Maleshevska-Pirin low mountain, Mestenski and Mountain climatic areas of the South Bulgarian climatic subregion (STANEV, 1991). Glacial lakes are situated in the cirques of the granite part of Northern Pirin whereas the marble part is relatively anhydrous. Pirin Mt. belongs to the same titled region of the Illyrian province of the European deciduous forest area. The vegetation is differentiated in a system of 6 vegetation zones (STOJANOV, 1966; VELCHEV et al., 1982, 1989; VELCHEV, TONKOV, 1986; BONDEV, 1991, 1997, 2002; VELCHEV, 1997, 2002): 1) Xerothermic oak forests, best presented in the west and south hillsides – to 600-700 m a.s.l.; 2) Mesophytic and xeromesophytic mixed forests, well presented in the southwest and east hillsides – from 600-700 m a.s.l. to 900-1000 m a.s.l.; 3) Beech forests, best presented in the middle and south parts of the mountain – from 900-1000 m a.s.l. to 1500-1600 m a.s.l.; 4) Coniferous forests – from 1300-1600 m a.s.l. to 2000-2200 m a.s.l.; 5) Subalpine vegetation – from 2000 to 2500 m a.s.l.; 6) Alpine vegetation – above 2400-2500 m a.s.l. For the coniferous zone of the marble part of the Northern Pirin, the Mediterranean plant formation of *Pinus leucodermis* Ait is typical. Pirin Mt. belongs to the Rila-Rhodope zoogeographical region and has an Eurosiberian and Submediterranean faunistic character in the lower parts (GEORGIEV, 1982, 2002).

The territory of the Pirin National Park includes 40332 ha with the reserves Bayuvi Dupki-Dzhindzhiritsa (2873 ha) and Yulen (3156 ha). The park's boundary descends lowest over Bansko – 800-900 m a.s.l. but usually lies significantly higher (above 1300-1700 m). The reserves Orelek (situated in Middle Pirin) and Tisata (situated in Kresna Gorge) remain outside the park's territory.

The material is collected after the First World War and the main part of it is stored in the National Museum of Natural History. A number of foreign entomologists have been collected and published

materials from Bulgaria, containing data about Pirin Mt. The material was collected from 77 localities (Table 1), grouped in 23 starting points: south of Gradevo village, Predel area, southwest of the towns Razlog and Bansko, the chalets Yavorov, Vihren and Demyanitsa, Dobrinishte village, Bezbog chalet, west of Momina Klisura, Gotse Delchev, Popovi Livadi area, Paril village, Teshovo village, Pirin village, Melnik, Pirin chalet, Sandanska Bistritsa River, Begovitsa chalet, east of Ploski village, Kresna, Vlahi village and Brezhani village. From the western and southwestern slopes of the mountain the territory above 300 m a.s.l. is included. The material collected beneath this altitude is not a subject of this study. A significant number of species are known from Kresna Gorge but they are collected mainly from the lower parts (below 300 m) and also are not included in this study. In some cases, the old collectors did not give an accurate localities on the labels and indicated only Pirin Mt. For a number of widespread and mass species the authors did not give the localities and mentioned they occur everywhere. Such species are included in the review only if they are reported from Pirin Mt.

Zoogeographical analysis for species categorization was used. This method allows obtaining data information about species complexes with different zoogeographical character based on the published data regarding species distribution and results of the sums. The classification of the areas is based on the works of DE LATTIN (1967), MALICKY et al. (1983), GORODKOV (1984) and VIGNA TAGLIANTI et al. (1999) but the inversion of the traditional zoogeographical nomenclature of VIGNA TAGLIANTI et al. (1999) is not accepted.

Abbreviations used: **figures** – numbers of the localities in Table 1 and numbers from the References, **Roman figures** – months of flight activity or period of collecting, **?** – uncertain data or lack of data, **atm** – Afrotropical-Mediterranean, **ban** – Balkan-Anatolian, **bm** – Boreomontane, **cse** – Central and South European, **csean** – Central and South European-Anatolian, **csee** – Central and Southeast European, **cseeit** – Central and Southeast European-Iran-Turanian, **cseit** – Central and South European-Iran-Turanian, **csena** – Central and South European-North African, **des** – Disjunct Eurosiberian, **dp** – Disjunct Palaearctic, **dpo** – Disjunct Palaearctic-Oriental, **e** – European, **ean** – European-Anatolian, **Eb** – Balkan endemic, **Ebg** – Bulgarian endemic, **Ebs** – Balkan subendemic, **eca** – European-Central Asian, **eeca** – East European-Central Asian, **eit** – European-Iran-Turanian, **em** –

Table 1. Localities of Diptera from Pirin Mt.

Localities	Altitude (m)	GPS Navigation (°N, °E)	UTM Kode	Number of species
1. Argirovo Lake	2365	41°41'30.79"; 23°30'30.75"	GM01	4
2. Banderitsa River basin, Banderitsa River valley	2000-2300	41°45'07.18"; 23°24'47.44"	FM92, GM02	8
3. Banderishki Lakes	2060-2350	41°44'09.76"; 23°25'18.66"	GM02	3
4. Banderitsa Chalet	1810	41°46'06.10"; 23°25'37.27"	GM02	53
5. Banderitsa Chalet, surroundings	1500-2000	41°45'47.17"; 23°25'13.94"	GM02	52
6. Banderitsa River, above Bansko	1200-1400	41°47'48.59"; 23°27'17.88"	GM03	16
7. Banderishko Ribno Lake (Golyamo Banderishko)	2190	41°44'18.29"; 23°24'54.62"	GM02	18
8. Bansko, surroundings	900-1000	41°49'39.29"; 23°28'28.72"	GM03	132
9. Bansko (above Bansko)	1000-1600	41°47'36.52"; 23°26'52.06"	GM03	45
10. Bansko – Vihren Chalet	1000-1500	41°47'36.69"; 23°26'52.55"	GM03, GM02	33
11. Bayuvi Dupki, near Yavorov Chalet	1500-2500	41°47'42.27"; 23°22'57.80"	FM93	2
12. Begovitsa (Kamenitsa) Chalet	1750	41°40'26.60"; 23°25'39.27"	GM01	8
13. Begovitsa (Kamenitsa) Chalet, surroundings	1750-2000	41°40'14.94"; 23°26'16.37"	GM01	19
14. Begovitsa River basin	1900-2200	41°40'41.76"; 23°27'44.23"	FM91, GM01	6
15. Begovitsa River valley	1300-1900	41°40'16.24"; 23°24'54.49"	FM91, GM01	11
16. Bezbog Lake	2240	41°43'59.96"; 23°31'27.92"	GM02	2
17. Bezbog Peak, surroundings	2240-2645	41°43'52.78"; 23°30'45.99"	GM02	11
18. Brezhani village (near Simitli, northeast of Krupnik)	500-700	41°51'49.33"; 23°11'10.39"	FM83	7
19. Breznitsa village	700-750	41°40'17.68"; 23°39'42.41"	GM21	16
20. Demyanitsa Chalet, surroundings	1800-2000	41°44'34.55"; 23°28'04.40"	GM02	23
21. Demyanishka Polyana	1800	41°45'08.72"; 23°27'59.05"	GM02	5
22. Demyanitsa River, near Bansko	900-1000	41°48'25.78"; 23°28'20.58"	GM03	11
23. Dobrinishte, surroundings	850-900	41°47'58.11"; 23°33'56.45"	GM13	44
23a. Dzhamdzhevi Skali, locality (near Banderitsa Chalet)	2270	41°46'01.10"; 23°24'49.04"	GM02	1
24. Gazeyski Lakes	2400-2640	41°43'39.24"; 23°29'09.02"	GM02	8
25. Gazey Peak, surroundings	2000-2500	41°43'57.48"; 23°29'03.75"	GM02	1
26. Georgiyiski (Gergiyiski) Lakes	2020-2392	41°44'45.06"; 23°22'49.44"	FM92	10
27. Gotse Deltshev (G. Deltshev – Gotse Deltshev Chalet)	600-1000	41°34'12.87"; 23°41'56.90"	GM20	29
28. Gotse Deltshev Chalet, surroundings	1475-1600	41°45'38.29"; 23°32'56.58"	GM20	33
29. Gradevska River, near Gradevo village	700-750	41°55'42.68"; 23°14'42.68"	FM84	14
30. Karlanovo village, surroundings, near Melnik	500-650	41°32'39.42"; 23°25'00.53"	GM00	4
31. Koprivlen village (above Koprivlen village)	600-700	41°30'39.45"; 23°47'22.74"	GM30	10
32. Kremenska (Lakinska) Reka River, near Kremen village	700-800	41°45'22.38"; 23°39'57.11"	GM12, GM22	5
33. Lilyanovo village, surroundings	450-700	41°37'03.16"; 23°18'58.64"	FM90, FM91	76
34. Melnik, surroundings	350-450	41°31'26.72"; 23°23'32.19"	FL99, GM00	139
35. Mesta village (above Mesta village)	700-800	41°45'35.94"; 23°40'10.27"	GM22	19
36. Mitrovo Lake (Demirkapiyski Lakes)	2292	41°41'16.92"; 23°30'06.80"	GM01	4
37. Muratovo Lake (Ovinato, Hvoynato, Banderishki Lakes)	2230	41°44'45.03"; 23°24'21.91"	FM92, GM02	10
38. Okoto Lake (above Vihren Chalet, Banderishki Lakes)	2060	41°45'06.22"; 23°24'54.38"	GM02	15
39. Parilska Sedlovina Col (South Pirin), surroundings	1170-1300	41°25'37.04"; 23°39'08.14"	GL28	24
40. Paril village, surroundings (above Paril)	700-900	41°26'03.06"; 23°40'43.45"	GL29	30
41. Pirin Mt., presence in Pirin is indicated	300-2914		FM83....GL29	47
42. Pirin Chalet	1640	41°37'56.48"; 23°29'47.45"	GM00	11
43. Pirin Chalet, surroundings	1600-2000	41°38'55.43"; 23°30'04.01"	GM00	8
44. Pirinska Bistritsa River (near Gorno Spanchevo village)	350-500	41°30'33.14"; 23°30'32.74"	GL09	3
45. Ploski village (above Ploski village)	500-650	41°38'42.09"; 23°16'00.02"	FM81	42

Table 1. Continued

Localities	Altitude (m)	GPS Navigation (°N, °E)	UTM Kode	Number of species
46. Popina Laka (above Lilyanovo village)	1250	41°40'19.99"; 23°23'34.95"	FM91	30
47. Popina Laka, surroundings	1230-1350	41°40'27.71"; 23°23'51.95"	GM01	82
48. Popovi Livadi (Papaz Chair, Popski Preslap)	1430	41°32'49.76"; 23°37'55.52"	GM10	29
49. Popovi Livadi (Papaz Chair) – Orelyak Massif	1500-2000	41°33'14.31"; 23°37'17.49"	GM10, GM20	11
50. Predela Col (west of Razlog)	1142	41°52'54.41"; 23°20'55.39"	FM93, FM94	51
51. Predela Col, surroundings	850-1150	41°53'52.95"; 23°19'19.61"	FM93, FM94	50
52. Prevalski Lakes (Demyanishki Lakes)	2330-2300	41°42'30.33"; 23°28'20.75"	GM02	2
53. Razlog (above Razlog – Betolovoto)	1000-1200	41°51'01.67"; 23°23'01.33"	GM03	88
54. Ribno (Golyamo) Banderishko Lake	2190	41°44'18.29"; 23°24'54.62"	GM02	5
55. Rozhen Monastery, near Melnik	650	41°31'50.10"; 23°25'36.33"	GM00	17
56. Rozhen Monastery, surroundings	550-650	41°31'49.82"; 23°25'35.40"	GM00	11
57. Rozhen village, near Melnik	300-500	41°32'05.62"; 23°26'00.46"	GM00	43
58. Sandanski (above Sandanski – Lilyanovo village)	300-400	41°35'50.10"; 23°17'52.40"	FM90	92
59. Sandanski Chalet (Popina Laka, surroundings)	1230	41°40'18.19"; 23°23'37.95"	GM01	19
60. Sandanska Bistritsa River, above Lilyanovo village	400-950	41°38'49.99"; 23°21'25.84"	FM91	7
61. Sharaliyska Peshtera Cave (above Ilindentsi village)	1600	41°42'47.00"; 23°18'51.00"	FM91	1
62. Shilignarnika (north of Todorin Peak)	1740	41°46'44.46"; 23°26'55.38"	GM02	6
63. Sinanitsa Chalet, Sinanishko Lake	2200	41°44'39.25"; 23°22'23.49"	FM92	1
64. South Pirin	300-1978		GL19, GL29, GM20	12
65. Stara Kresna village (above Stara Kresna village)	450-650	41°47'23.62"; 23°10'51.41"	FM82	7
66. Todorini Lakes (Todorini Ochi, Ochite na Todorka)	2510-2550	41°44'52.28"; 23°26'00.14"	GM02	10
67. Todorin Preval (Preval na Malka Todorka)	2575	41°44'28.46"; 23°25'51.54"	GM02	3
68. Tremoshnitsa, locality (above Lilyanovo village)	900-1000	41°39'24.51"; 23°22'13.16"	FM91	67
69. Vasilashki Lakes	2126-2362	41°44'27.30"; 23°26'49.62"	GM02	13
70. Vihren Chalet	1950	41°45'23.57"; 23°25'01.06"	GM02	22
71. Vihren Chalet, surroundings	1900-2500	41°44'48.97"; 23°24'43.46"	GM02, FM92	48
72. Vihren Peak, surroundings	2500-2900	41°46'50.06"; 23°23'50.18"	FM92	7
73. Vlahi village, surroundings	500-700	41°44'19.40"; 23°13'49.67"	FM82	8
74. Vlahinska Reka River (above Vlahi village)	500-750	41°43'52.72"; 23°16'15.40"	FM82	5
75. Yavorov Chalet	1740	41°49'32.54"; 23°22'42.27"	FM93	26
76. Yavorov Chalet, surroundings	1740-1900	41°49'04.86"; 23°23'29.91"	FM93	14
77. Zhabeshko Lake (Banderishki Lakes)	2322	41°44'19.76"; 23°25'24.45"	GM02	7

East Mediterranean, **ena** – European-North African, **Er** – Regional endemic, **esca** – Eurosiberian-Central Asian, **ess** – European and South Siberian, **eswa** – European-Southwest Asian, **et** – European-Turanian, **ewca** – European-West Central Asian, **h** – Holarctic, **h*** – species introduced in North America, **ha** – Holarctic-Australian, **hat** – Holarctic-Afrotropical, **hn** – Holarctic-Neotropical, **hnat** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Afrotropical, **hno** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental, **hnoa** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental-Australian, **ho** – Holarctic-Oriental, **hoes** – Holoeurosiberian, **hom** – Holomediterranean, **hop** – Holopalaeartic, **hpt** – Holarctic-Paleotropical, **hpta** – Holarctic-Paleotropical-Australian,

hptn – Holarctic-Paleotropical-Neotropical, **k** – Cosmopolitan, **mca** – Mediterranean-Central Asian, **m** – montane, **mss** – Mediterranean and South Siberian, **msws** – Mediterranean and Southwest Siberian, **mt** – Mediterranean-Turanian, **mwca** – Mediterranean-West Central Asian, **nemit** – Northeast Mediterranean-Iran-Turanian, **nm** – North Mediterranean, **nmt** – North Mediterranean-Turanian, **NP** – Pirin National Park, **om** – Oriental-Mediterranean, **pa** – Palaeartic-Australian, **pat** – Palaeartic-Afrotropical, **po** – Palaeartic-Oriental, **poa** – Palaeartic-Oriental-Australian, **ppt** – Palaeartic-Paleotropical, **ppta** – Palaeartic-Paleotropical-Australian, **ptm** – Paleotropical-

Mediterranean, **se** – South European, **sess** – South European and South Siberian, **sk** – Semicosmopolitan, **sp** – South Palaearctic, **spat** – South Palaearctic-Afrotropical, **sppta** – South Palaearctic-Paleotropical-Australian, **tp** – Transpalaearctic, **wces** – West and Central Eurosiberian, **wcp** – West and Central Palaearctic, **wes** – West Eurosiberian, **wesca** – West Eurosiberian-Central Asian, **wp** – West Palaearctic, **wpat** – West Palaearctic-Afrotropical, **wpo** – West Palaearctic-Oriental.

Results and discussion

A total of 742 species dipterans (18.5% of the species found in Bulgaria) belonging to 43 families have been established in Pirin Mt. so far (Table 2). The family Tachinidae is most numerous – 203, followed by Limoniidae – 72, Chloropidae – 72, Cecidomyiidae – 54, Syrphidae – 49, Muscidae – 49 and Ephydriidae – 33 species. The remaining families contain from 1 to 18 species. The taxa distribution in most cases is connected with the exploration of the corresponding mountain region. This is evident when comparing the established species in regard to the localities (Table 1). Six areas of good research (over 70 species found) are outlined. First are the surroundings of Bansko (132 species) and Melnik (139 species) – the most visited places at the foot of the mountain. The popular resorts and starting points for entering Pirin Mt. – Sandanski and Lilyanovo village, Popina laka and Razlog (from 77 to 92 species) also form a group of well-studied regions. Of the inner parts of the mountain, the surroundings of the chalets Banderitsa, Vihren, Gotse Delchev, Yavorov and Demyanitsa are better studied (from 23 to 53 species). It is seen that the localities from which a material is collected (only 77) are concentrated around the popular tourist centers or routes (when they are not near the chalets). Significant parts of the mountain are unexplored and material is not collected. This relates both to the difficult of approach terrain and the insufficiently investigation of the separate families. The number of the established species probably represents about 35-40% of the actual species composition of the investigated territory. The dipterans are a highly mobile group and after further investigations of Pirin Mt. can be expected to reach 40-50% of the species composition of most families found in the country.

A total of 559 species has been established in the Pirin National Park. In comparison with the Central Balkan National Park – 184 species (HUBENOV et al., 2000a), Rila National Park – 386 species (HUBENOV et

al., 2000b), East Rhodopes – 279 species (HUBENOV, 2004) and Vitosha Mt. – 1000 species (HUBENOV, 2014), the family Tachinidae (147 species) which is systematically studied only in Pirin Mt., should be dropped out. Thus 410 species remain in the Pirin National Park' territory which is commensurable with the Diptera fauna of the Rila National Park (better studied), significantly exceeds the Central Balkan National Park and considerably decreases vis-a-vis Vitosha Mt. It should be kept in mind that Vitosha is the most studied Bulgarian mountain and its whole territory is used for comparison (not only Vitosha Park) while the Central Balkan National Park is poorly investigated with respect to the two-winged insects. When comparing the whole Pirin Mt. with Vitosha Mt., the difference is not large although the insufficiently research of Pirin Mt. It is expected, under further investigations, Pirin Mt. to exceed most of our mountains in species composition of Diptera. This relates to the wide variety of natural habitats as well as the geographical location which the mountain occupies in southwestern Bulgaria, on the border between the Eurosiberian and Mediterranean Palaearctic subregions.

In the xerothermic oak forests belt 257 species (34.7%) have been established, despite its limited development in western, southwestern and southern parts of the mountain. This is connected with its open spaces to which species of Sandanski-Petrich Valley penetrate. Most species have been found in the beech forests (394 species – 53.2%) and the mesophilic and xeromesophilic mixed forests (364 species – 49.2%). The border between the beech and the coniferous forests of Pirin Mt. is not clear and depending on the exposure, relief and anthropogenic impact, there are wide areas of mixing (200-300 m a.s.l.). This determines the high species richness in the beech belt, the great number of common species and the similarity of the Diptera fauna from II to IV vegetation belt. In regard to the hypsometric belts, the maximum number of species is located between 900 and 1300 m a.s.l. The upper limit of the coniferous zone gradually passes into the sub-alpine vegetation zones with a mixture regions of about 200 m a.s.l. Thus most of the species are common to both vegetation belts and the number of taxa established in the sub-alpine belt increases. Of the species found in the alpine belt, there is no one typical for it only. All these species have been established in the sub-alpine belt and most of them – in the other vegetation belts as well. In some cases, finding of species at certain altitude takes place accidentally. The lack of systematic research on the Diptera of Pirin Mt. and

Table 2. Species composition of the dipterans (Insecta: Diptera) of Pirin Mt.

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical	
NEMATOCERA					
TIPULOMORPHA					
Limoniidae / 72		70			
<i>Austrolimnophila (Austrolimnophila) ochracea</i> (Meigen, 1804)	46	+	1250	eit	VI 87
<i>Dactylobasis (Dactylobasis) transversa</i> (Meigen, 1804)	5	+	1700	cse	VI 86
<i>Epiphragma (Epiphragma) ocellare ocellare</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	46	+	1250	h	VI 87
<i>Eloephila maculata</i> (Meigen, 1804)	51		1142	et	VI 96
<i>Eloephila mundata</i> (Loew, 1871)	13, 47	+	1230-2000	e	VIII 87
<i>Neolimnomyia (Brachylimnophila) nemoralis</i> (Meigen, 1818)	4, 13, 47	+	1230-1810	tp	VI 86, 109
<i>Phylidorea (Macrolabina) alexanderi</i> (Stary, 1974)	12	+	1750	Ebg	VI 86, 109
<i>Ptilaria fuscipennis</i> (Meigen, 1818)	71, 72	+	1960-2914	des	VIII 86
<i>Prionolabis hospes</i> (Egger, 1863)	6, 14, 47	+	1300-2200	cse	VI 87
<i>Pseudolimnophila (Pseudolimnophila) sepium</i> (Verrall, 1886)	71	+	2100	eit	VI 87
<i>Erioptera (Erioptera) griseipennis</i> Meigen, 1838	8	+	1000	e	VI 87
<i>Erioptera (Erioptera) lutea</i> Meigen, 1804	6, 12, 46, 71	+	1200-1700	wcp	VI, VIII 86, 87
<i>Gonempeda flava</i> (Schummel, 1829)	8	+	1000	e	VI 87
<i>Scleroprocta balcanica</i> Stary, 1976	15, 47	+	1230-1350	Eb	VI, VIII 86, 87, 111
<i>Symplecta (Symplecta) hybrida</i> (Meigen, 1804)	22	+	900-1000	ho	V-VIII, X 87
<i>Cheilotrichia (Empeda) staryi</i> Mendl, 1973	2, 14	+	1900-2300	cse	VIII-IX 86, 87
<i>Eriocnopa symplectoides</i> (Kuntze, 1914)	2	+	2100	hom	VI 111
<i>Eriocnopa trivialis</i> (Meigen, 1818)	14	+	1900-2000	eit	VIII 109
<i>Ilisia maculata</i> (Meigen, 1804)	8	+	1000	eit	VI 87
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) aduncus</i> Stary, 1978	8, 22	+	900-1000	nmt	VIII 86, 112
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) appendiculatus</i> (Staeger, 1840)	70	+	1950	wes	VIII-IX 86, 112
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) brevipennis</i> Bangert, 1947	8, 22, 47	+	900-1230	csee	VI-VIII 87
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) curvatus</i> Tonnoir, 1920	47	+	1230	e	VI 87
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) directidens</i> Stary, 1976	13, 47, 71	+	1230-2000	Ebg	VIII-IX 86, 111
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) flagellatus</i> Stary, 1976	13	+	1900-2000	Ebg	VIII-IX 86, 111
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) lanceolatus</i> Stary, 1971	15	+	1400	Er	VI 108
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) medius</i> Meijere, 1918	49		1500	e	VI, VIII 87

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) obscurus</i> (Meigen, 1818)	8	+	1000	can	V-VIII 87
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) obsoletus</i> Lackschewitz, 1940	5	+	1700	Ebs	VI-VII 87
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) ochraceus</i> (Meigen, 1818)	8	+	1000	e	VI, VIII 87
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) priapoides</i> Starý, 1971	5, 8	+	1000-1850	e	VI 86, 107
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) propinquus</i> (Egger, 1863)	6, 9, 22	+	900-1200	tp	VI, VIII 87
<i>Ormosia (Ormosia) bifida</i> (Lackschewitz, 1940)	5, 71	+	1700-2000	e, ? cse	VI, VIII 86, 87
<i>Ormosia (Ormosia) fascipennis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	4, 6	+	1200-1900	h	VI 87
<i>Ormosia (Ormosia) pirinensis</i> Starý, 1971	5, 6	+	1400	Ebg	VI, IX 86, 87, 107
<i>Ormosia (Ormosia) staegeriana</i> Alexander, 1953	13, 47	+	1400-1800	e	VIII-IX 87
<i>Rhypholophus bifurcatus</i> Goetghebuer, 1920	71	+	2000	e	VIII 86
<i>Rhypholophus haemorrhoidalis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	71	+	2000	e	VIII-IX 86
<i>Rhypholophus phryganopterus</i> Kolenati, 1860	2, 4, 71	+	1700-2400	cse, ? e	VI 86, 87
<i>Dicranoptycha cinerascens</i> (Meigen, 1818)	71	+	2000	e	VIII 87
<i>Dicranoptycha fuscescens</i> (Schummel, 1829)	47	+	1230-1350	wp	VI 87
<i>Dicranoptycha livescens</i> Loew, 1871	71	+	2000	cse, ? e	VIII 87
<i>Dicranoptycha paralivescens</i> Starý, 1972	71	+	2000	cse	VIII 87
<i>Gonomyia (Gonomyia) conoviensis</i> Barnes, 1924	47	+	1230-1350	eit	VI 87
<i>Gonomyia (Gonomyia) lucidula</i> Meijere, 1920	8, 47	+	1000-1350	e	VI 87
<i>Gonomyia (Gonomyia) tenella</i> (Meigen, 1818)	22, 71	+	900-2000	ena	VI, VIII 86, 87
<i>Gonomyia (Teuchogonomyia) edwardsi</i> Lackschewitz, 1925	6	+	1200	e	VI 87
<i>Idiocera (Idiocera) pulchripennis</i> (Loew, 1856)	8	+	1000	? mwca	VII-VIII 86, 110
<i>Lipsothrix errans</i> (Walker, 1848)	47	+	1230-1350	e	VI 87
<i>Lipsothrix remota</i> (Walker, 1848)	47	+	1230-1350	e	VI 87
<i>Antocha (Antocha) vitripennis</i> (Meigen, 1830)	4	+	1810	ewca	VI 86, 109
<i>Antocha (Orimargula) alpigena</i> (Mik, 1883)	13, 47, 71	+	1230-2000	e	VI, VIII 86, 87
<i>Orimarga (Orimarga) attenuata</i> (Walker, 1848)	14	+	2000-2200	ena	VI 87
<i>Orimarga (Orimarga) juvenilis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1851)	8	+	1000	e	VI 87
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) chorea</i> (Meigen, 1818)	5, 6	+	1200-1700	h	VI 87
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) conchifera</i> (Strobl, 1901)	47	+	1230-1350	cse, ? e	VI 87
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) mitis</i> (Meigen, 1830)	6, 15, 46, 49	+	1300-1900	wp	VI, VIII 87

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) signata</i> (Lackschewitz, 1941)	8	+	1000	em	VI	87, 96
<i>Dicranomyia (Melanolimonia) caledonica</i> Edwards, 1926	5, 15, 47	+	1300-1800	hoes	VI	87
<i>Dicranomyia (Numantia) fusca</i> (Meigen, 1804)	71	+	1900-2000	h	VIII	86
<i>Limonia flavipes</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	4, 47	+	1230-1810	ena	VI	86, 87, 109
<i>Limonia hercegovinae</i> (Strobl, 1898)	6	+	1200	? eit	VI	87
<i>Limonia macrostigma</i> (Schummel, 1829)	5, 47	+	1200-1700	po	VI, VIII	87
<i>Limonia nigropunctata</i> (Schummel, 1829)	47, 13	+	1300-1800	e	VI	87
<i>Limonia nubeculosa</i> Meigen, 1804	71	+	2000	h	V, VIII	86, 87
<i>Limonia pannonica</i> (Kowarz, 1868)	47	+	1230-1350	cse	V-VI	87
<i>Limonia phragmitidis</i> (Schränk, 1781)	47	+	1230-1350	wp	V-VI	87
<i>Limonia stigma</i> (Meigen, 1818)	2, 47	+	1250-2300	e	VIII	87
<i>Limonia sylvicola</i> (Schummel, 1829)	5	+	1600-1700	wces	VIII-IX	86, 87, 109
<i>Limonia taurica</i> (Strobl, 1895)	13, 47	+	1300-1800	can	V-VI	87
<i>Neolimonia dumetorum</i> (Meigen, 1804)	47	+	1230-1350	e	VI, VIII	87
<i>Rhipidia (Rhipidia) maculata</i> Meigen, 1818	6, 70	+	1200-1950	h	VI, VIII	86, 87
Pediciidae / 6						
<i>Dicranota (Ludivia) lucidipennis</i> (Edwards, 1921)	4, 13, 47	+	1230-1810	cse, ? e	VI-VII	86, 109
<i>Dicranota (Paradicranota) subtilis</i> Loew, 1871	47	+	1230-1350	e	VI	87
<i>Pedicia (Amalopsis) occulta</i> (Meigen, 1830)	5, 13	+	1600-2000	eswa	VI, VIII	86, 87, 109
<i>Pedicia (Pedicia) rivosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	12	+	1750	wes	VIII	86, 109
<i>Tricyphona (Tricyphona) immaculata</i> (Meigen, 1804)	2, 14	+	1900-2200	? wp	V-VI, VIII	87
<i>Tricyphona (Tricyphona) livida</i> Madarassy, 1881	71	+	2000	e	VIII-IX	86
BIBIONOMORPHA						
Mycetophilidae / 18						
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) cinerascens</i> (Macquart, 1826)	75	+	1740	ho	IV-X	8
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) flavicollis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1852)	75	+	1740	e	V-IX	8
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) marginata</i> (Meigen, 1818)	75	+	1740	po	IV-XI	8
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) tenuis</i> (Walker, 1856)	75	+	1740	e	VI-VIII	8
<i>Mycomya (Mycomyopsis) trilineata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	75	+	1740	hoes	VI-VIII	8
<i>Boletina plana</i> (Walker, 1856)	75	+	1740	hoes	VI-VII	8

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Boletina sciarina</i> Staeger, 1840	76	+	1740-1800	h	IV-VII	6, 8
<i>Acnemia nitidicollis</i> (Meigen, 1818)	75	+	1740	des	VI-IX	8
<i>Polylepta guttiventris</i> (Zetterstedt, 1852)	75	+	1740	h	V-X	8
<i>Sciophila lutea</i> Macquart, 1826	50		1142	tp	IV-VII	8
<i>Sciophila rufa</i> Meigen, 1830	50		1142	hoes	VI	8
<i>Leia bimaculata</i> (Meigen, 1804)	50		1142	tp	V-X	8
<i>Mycetophila blanda</i> Winnertz, 1863	20	+	2000	wces	V-X	8
<i>Mycetophila confluens</i> Dziedzicki, 1884	20	+	2000	des	IV-IX	8
<i>Mycetophila czizekii</i> Landrock, 1911	20	+	2000	e	V, VII-XI	8
<i>Mycetophila marginata</i> Winnertz, 1863	20	+	2000	e	IV-X	8
<i>Mycetophila ocellus</i> Walker, 1848	20	+	2000	h	IV-XI	8
<i>Mycetophila stylata</i> (Dziedzicki, 1884)	20	+	2000	hoes	VIII	8
Bolitophiliidae / 5		4				
<i>Bolitophila (Bolitophila) cinerea</i> Meigen, 1818	75	+	1740	hoes	VI-VIII	6, 7
<i>Bolitophila (Bolitophila) saundersii</i> (Curtis, 1836)	76	+	1740-1800	tp	V-XI	6, 7
<i>Bolitophila (Chiopisa) oclusa</i> Edwards, 1913	75	+	1740	des	VII	6, 7
<i>Bolitophila (Chiopisa) pseudohybrida</i> Landrock, 1912	55		650	des	V-VI, XI	6, 7
<i>Bolitophila (Chiopisa) rossica</i> Landrock, 1912	20	+	2000	des	VIII	5, 7
Diadocidiidae / 1		1				
<i>Diadocidia (Diadocidia) spinosula</i> Tollef, 1948	75	+	1740	e	VI-IX	6, 7
Keroplastidae / 3						
<i>Orfelia nemoralis</i> (Meigen, 1818)	30		500	e	V-VII	6, 7
<i>Orfelia tristis</i> (Lundström, 1911)	48		1430	e	V-VII	6, 7
<i>Pyratula zonata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1855)	56		550	e	V-VI	6, 7
Macroceridae / 4		4				
<i>Macrocera centralis</i> Meigen, 1818	5	+	1700-1820	wes	V-IX	6, 7
<i>Macrocera inversa</i> Loew, 1869	75	+	1740	wes	V-VII	6, 7
<i>Macrocera parva</i> Lundström, 1914	75	+	1740	wces	VI-VIII	6, 7
<i>Macrocera stigmoides</i> Edwards, 1925	5, 76	+	1700-1820	e	V-VIII	6, 7
Cecidomyiidae / 54		29				

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical	
				Fenology	
<i>Lasioptera eryngii</i> (Vallot, 1829)	23		850	ena	V-VI 104
<i>Bayeriola capitigena</i> (Bremsi, 1847)	10, 23, 50	+	850-1300	e	V-IX 104
<i>Bayeriola thymicola</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	23		850	ena	VI-VIII 104
<i>Cystiphona taraxaci</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	8	+	980	e	VI 104
<i>Dasineura asperulae</i> (Löw, 1875)	23		850	cse	VI 104
<i>Dasineura crataegi</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	23, 34		350-850	e	VI-IX 98, 104
<i>Dasineura flicina</i> (Kieffer, 1889)	11	+	1500-2500	des	VI-VIII 98
<i>Dasineura galiicola</i> (Löw, 1880)	51		1100	e	VI 104
<i>Dasineura hyperici</i> (Bremsi, 1848)	8, 23, 50, 71	+	850-1300	e	VI-IX 104
<i>Dasineura plicatrix</i> (Loew, 1850)	10	+	1100-1300	ena	V-IX 104
<i>Dasineura potentillae</i> (Wachtl, 1885)	10	+	1300	e	VI 104
<i>Dasineura schulzei</i> (Rübsaamen, 1917)	9, 10, 50	+	1100-1300	csee	VI 104
<i>Dasineura sisymbrii</i> (Schrank, 1803)	8	+	980-1000	e	V-IX 104
<i>Dasineura thomasiana</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	8		980	e	VI-VIII 104
<i>Dasineura tortilis</i> (Bremsi, 1847)	10, 51	+	1000-1100	e	VI 104
<i>Dasineura tortrix</i> (Löw, 1877)	10, 51	+	1100-1300	e	VI-VIII 104
<i>Dasineura trifolii</i> (Löw, 1874)	8, 51	+	900-1100	h	VI-VIII 104
<i>Dasineura ulmaria</i> (Bremsi, 1847)	8	+	1000	des	VI-VIII 104
<i>Dasineura urticae</i> (Perris, 1840)	8, 51	+	980-1100	des	VI-VIII 104
<i>Rabdophaga heterobia</i> (Loew, 1850)	10, 51	+	1100-1300	dp	VI, IX 104
<i>Rabdophaga saliciperda</i> (Dufour, 1841)	10	+	1300	dp	IV-VI 104
<i>Rabdophaga salicis</i> (Schrank, 1803)	10	+	1300	h	V-VIII 104
<i>Rabdophaga terminalis</i> (Loew, 1850)	8, 10	+	980-1300	tp	VI-VIII 104
<i>Dryomyia circinans</i> (Giraud, 1861)	34		450	dp	VI-IX 98
<i>Geocrypta galii</i> (Loew, 1850)	10, 23, 50	+	1000-1300	des	VI-VIII 104
<i>Hartigiola annulipes</i> (Hartig, 1839)	41			dp	VI-IX 98
<i>Iteomyia capreae</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	51		1100	tp	VI, VIII, X 104
<i>Jaapiella bryoniae</i> (Bouche, 1847)	8	+	980-1000	ena	VI 104
<i>Jaapiella cucubali</i> (Kieffer, 1909)	23		850	cse	VI-VIII 104
<i>Jaapiella veronicae</i> (Vallot, 1827)	51		1100	e	VI, IX 104

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Fabomya medicaginis</i> (Rübsaamen, 1912)	23		850	wes	VI, IX	104
<i>Janetiella thymi</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	9, 10, 50	+	1100-1300	e	VI	104
<i>Macrolabis heraclei</i> Kaltenbach, 1862	8		980	e	VI-VIII	104
<i>Macrolabis lamii</i> Rübsaamen, 1916	8		980	e	VI-VIII	104
<i>Macrolabis stallariae</i> (Liebel, 1889)	8		980	e	VI	104
<i>Phegomyia fagicola</i> (Kieffer, 1901)	51		1100	e	VI	104
<i>Mikiola fagi</i> (Hartig, 1839)	51		1100	des	IV-XII	98, 104
<i>Oligotrophus juniperinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	10, 23	+	850-1300	e	VI-X	98, 104
<i>Oligotrophus panteli</i> (Kieffer, 1898)	10, 23	+	850-1300	ena	VI-VIII	98, 104
<i>Semudobia betulae</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	10, 23	+	850-1100	h	VI-IX	104
<i>Semudobia skuhravae</i> Roskam, 1977	10, 23	+	850-1100	h	VI-IX	104
<i>Wachtliella rosarum</i> (Hardy, 1850)	10, 23	+	850-1300	h	V-IX	104
<i>Wachtliella stachydis</i> (Brems, 1847)	51		1100	e	VI	104
<i>Zygiobia carpini</i> (Löw, 1874)	51		1100	e	VI-IX	104
<i>Asphondylia cytisi</i> Frauenfeld, 1873	10	+	1300	wes	VI-VIII	104
<i>Aschistonyx carpinicola</i> Rübsaamen, 1917	51		1100	e	VI-VII	104
<i>Contarinia anthobia</i> (Löw, 1877)	10	+	1300	e	VI	104
<i>Contarinia baeri</i> (Prell, 1931)	10, 23	+	850-1300	des	VI	104
<i>Contarinia fagi</i> Rübsaamen, 1921	51		1100	e	VI, IX	104
<i>Contarinia nasturtii</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	51		850-1100	ean	VI	104
<i>Contarinia quinquenotata</i> (Löw, 1888)	8		980	e	VI	104
<i>Mycodiplosis coniothega</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	10	+	1300	h	VI	104
<i>Mycodiplosis saundersi</i> Barnes, 1927	8		1000	e	VI-VIII	104
<i>Putoniella pruni</i> Kaltenbach, 1872	23		850	e	V-VII	104
Ptychopteridae / 1						
<i>Ptychoptera (Ptychoptera) albimana</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	33		500	h	VI	3
CULICOMORPHA						
Simuliidae / 10		7				
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) rufipes</i> (Meigen, 1830)	6, 48	+	1200-1400	ena	VI-VII	84
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) bertrandi</i> Gremier et Dorier, 1959	70	+	1950	e	VI-VII	84

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) carpathicum</i> (Knoz, 1961)	2	+	2000	e	VII-VIII	84
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) codreanui</i> (Serban, 1958)	70	+	1950	e	VII-VIII	84
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) cryophilum</i> (Rubzov, 1959)	29		700-750	ena	VI-IX	84
<i>Simulium (Hellichella) latipes</i> Meigen, 1804	38	+	2060	tp, ? h	IV-VII	84
<i>Simulium (Eusimulium) angustipes</i> Edwards, 1915	16	+	2240	wp	VII	84
<i>Simulium (Simulium) maximum</i> Knoz, 1961	44		450	e	VI	84
<i>Simulium (Simulium) degrangei</i> Dortier et Grenier, 1959	74		700	cse	VI	84
<i>Simulium (Simulium) argenteostriatum</i> Strobl, 1898	6, 32, 74	+	700-1300	csena	V-IX	84
Ceratopogonidae / 1						
<i>Dasyhelea (Dasyhelea) bilineata</i> Goetghebuer 1920	7	+	2090-2190	? tp	VI-VIII	116
Chironomidae / 13						
<i>Larsia curticalcar</i> (Kieffer, 1918)	1, 26	+	2020-2365	e	IV, VI, X	113
<i>Pseudodiamesa (Pseudodiamesa) branickii</i> (Nawicki, 1873)	50, 70	+	1140-1950	ho		97
<i>Acrictopus lucens</i> (Zetterstedt, 1850)	50, 70	+	1140-1950	h		97
<i>Cricotopus (Cricotopus) algarum</i> (Kieffer, 1911)	26	+	2020-2394	e	V-VI, VIII	113
<i>Cricotopus (Cricotopus) annulatus</i> Goetghebuer, 1927	1	+	2365	h	VI-VII	113
<i>Cricotopus (Isocladius) sylvestris</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	1, 26	+	2020-2365	hno	V-VIII	113
<i>Rheocricotopus (Rheocricotopus) effusus</i> (Walker, 1856)	50, 70	+	1140-1950	ho		97
<i>Chironomus (Chironomus) plumosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	26	+	2020-2394	hno	IV-X	113
<i>Chironomus (Chironomus) riparius</i> Meigen, 1804	1, 26	+	2020-2365	ho	V-X	113
<i>Cryptochironomus (Cryptochironomus) defectus</i> (Kieffer, 1913)	26	+	2020-2394	pa	IV-VIII	113
<i>Stictochironomus pictulus</i> (Meigen, 1830)	26	+	2020-2394	h		113
<i>Micropectra lindrothi</i> Goetghebuer, 1931	50		1142	h		97
<i>Micropectra notescens</i> (Walker, 1856)	70	+	1950	ena		97
BRACHYCERA ORTHORRHAPHA						
STRATIOMYOMORPHA						
Stratiomyidae / 12						
<i>Beris chalybata</i> (Forster, 1771)	41			e		47
<i>Chloromyia formosa</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	8, 34, 58	+	300-1000	h	V-VIII	1
<i>Chloromyia speciosa</i> (Macquart, 1834)	58		300-400	tp	VI-VIII	1

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Odontomyia hydroleon</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58		300-400	tp	VI-VII	1
<i>Oplodontha viridula</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	58		300-400	tp	VI-VIII	1
<i>Stratiomys chamaeleon</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	+	900-1000	esca	V-VI	1
<i>Stratiomys ruficornis</i> (Macquart, 1838)	41		1200	? cseit	V-VIII	103
<i>Lasioptera balius</i> (Walker, 1849)	8, 34, 58	+	300-1000	ban	V-VIII	1
<i>Lasioptera villosa</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	34		350-450	? cseit	V-VIII	1
<i>Oxycera nigricornis</i> Olivier, 1812	33, 58		300-500	e	VI-VIII	103
<i>Oxycera trilineata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58		300-400	wcp	VI	103
<i>Pachygaster atra</i> (Panzer, 1798)	34		350-450	eswa	VI-VIII	1
TABANOMORPHA						
Rhagionidae / 8						
<i>Chrysopilus cristatus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	9	+	1000-1200	e	VI-VIII	105
<i>Chrysopilus pullus</i> (Löw, 1869)	8	+	1000	e	VI	105
<i>Chrysopilus splendidus</i> (Meigen, 1820)	8	+	1000	e	VI-VIII	105
<i>Rhagio conspicuus</i> Meigen, 1804	5	+	1700-1800	e	V-VII	105
<i>Rhagio lineola</i> Fabricius, 1794	9	+	1000-1100	des	VI	105
<i>Rhagio scolopaceus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	+	1000	wes	V-VI	105
<i>Rhagio tringarius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	34		350-450	wes	IV-VIII	105
<i>Rhagio vitripennis</i> (Meigen, 1820)	8	+	1000	e	V-VI	105
Tabanidae / 5						
<i>Chrysops (Petersenichrysopterus) hamatus</i> Loew, 1858	58		300-400	ban	VII	40
<i>Hybomitra aterrina</i> (Meigen, 1820)	10	+	1500	cse	VII-VIII	42
<i>Hybomitra auripila</i> (Meigen, 1820)	10	+	1500	e	VII-VIII	42, 49
<i>Tabanus spodopterus</i> Meigen, 1820	8	+	1000	? csean	V-VIII	42
<i>Philpomyia aprica</i> (Meigen, 1820)	41			eit, ? cseit	VI-VII	100
Acroceridae / 1						
<i>Ogcodes (Ogcodes) lautereri</i> Chvala, 1980	2, 72	+	2000-2500 ?	hom	VII	38a
Asilidae / 11						
<i>Chorades fuliginosa</i> (Panzer, 1798)	8	+	1000	? wces	V-VIII	65
<i>Laphria flava</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	+	1000	po	V-VIII	65

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Dioctria oelandica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	+	1000	e	V-VII	65, 66
<i>Pycnopogon fasciculatus</i> (Loew, 1847)	58		300-400	hom	IV	66
<i>Molobratia teutonius</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	8	+	1000	eca	V-VII	65
<i>Leptarthrus brevis</i> (Meigen, 1804)	8	+	1000	e	VI	65
<i>Didymachus pictipes</i> (Meigen, 1820)	8	+	1000	wes	VI-VIII	65
<i>Dysmachus stylifer</i> (Loew, 1854)	8	+	1000	cse	V-VIII	65
<i>Machimus caliginosus</i> (Meigen, 1820)	8	+	1000	csean	V-VII	65
<i>Neotamias impudicus</i> (Gerstaecker, 1862)	8	+	1000	Eb	VI	65
<i>Philonicus albiceps</i> (Meigen, 1820)	8	+	1000	tp	V-VIII	65
Empididae / 7		6				
<i>Hilara discoidalis</i> Lundbeck, 1910	72	+	2500	e	VII	26
<i>Hilara setipes</i> Straka, 1976	15, 47	+	1230-1900	Ebg		115
<i>Empis (Empis) prodromus</i> Loew, 1867	8	+	900-1000	e	VI-VII	26
<i>Rhamphomyia (Rhamphomyia) morio</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	37, 38, 70	+	1950-2230	e	VII-VIII	48
<i>Rhamphomyia (Pararhamphomyia) simplex</i> (Zetterstedt, 1849)	4	+	1810	e	V-VII	48
<i>Rhamphomyia (Holoclera) trigemina</i> Oldenberg, 1927	4	+	1810	e	VI-VII	48
<i>Phaenobolia dimidiata</i> (Loew, 1869)	41			e, ? cse	VII	77
Hybotidae / 3						
<i>Platypalpus maculipes</i> (Meigen, 1829)	41			e	V	39
<i>Platypalpus nigritarsis</i> (Fallén, 1816)	41			e	VI	25
<i>Crossopalpus humilis</i> (Frey, 1913)	41			wes	VI	39
Dolichopodidae / 6		6				
<i>Hydrophorus balticus</i> (Meigen, 1824)	26	+	2020-2394	ppt	V-VIII	12
<i>Hercostomus fugax</i> (Loew, 1857)	38	+	2000	hoes	VIII	27
<i>Hercostomus labiatus</i> (Loew, 1857)	4, 36, 70	+	1600-2200	e, cse	VIII	27
<i>Dolichopus albipalpus</i> Negrobov, 1973	37, 38	+	2000-2200	dp	VIII	27
<i>Dolichopus beschovskii</i> Negrobov & Kechev, 2010	38	+	2200	Er	VIII	99
<i>Dolichopus pyrenaicus</i> Parent, 1920	37, 38, 54, 71	+	1800-2200	wes	VIII	27
BRACHYCERA CYCLORRHAPHA						
ASCHIZA						

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
Phoridae / 2						
<i>Aenigmatias franzi</i> Schmitz, 1950	23a	+	2270	des, ? wces	VII-IX	88a
<i>Triphleba antricola</i> (Schmitz, 1918)	61		1648	e	III-XII	11, 88
Pipunculidae / 14						
<i>Verrallia aucta</i> (Fallén, 1817)	58		300-400	h		89
<i>Eudorylas fuscus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	49		1500	e	VII	89
<i>Eudorylas ruralis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	12, 58	+	300-1750	ena, ? wp	V, VIII	28, 89
<i>Eudorylas subterminalis</i> Collin, 1956	6, 60	+	400-1400	e		89
<i>Eudorylas terminalis</i> (Thompson, 1869)	46, 48	+	1250-1430	e		89
<i>Eudorylas zonellus</i> (Collin, 1956)	60		400-950	e		89
<i>Dasydorylas horridus</i> (Becker, 1897)	58		300-400	e	VI	89
<i>Dorylomorpha (Dorylomorpha) confusa</i> (Verrall, 1901)	15, 46	+	1250-1900	e		89
<i>Dorylomorpha (Dorylomomyia) incognita</i> (Verrall, 1901)	14	+	1900-2000	e		89
<i>Tomosvaryella coquilletti</i> (Kertész, 1907)	5, 60	+	400-1900	ho	IV-IX	28, 89
<i>Tomosvaryella geniculata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	58		300-400	e	VI-VIII	89
<i>Tomosvaryella kuthyi</i> (Aczél, 1944)	60		400-950	ean		89
<i>Tomosvaryella nutata</i> (Becker, 1898)	55		650	hom	IX	28
<i>Tomosvaryella sylvatica</i> (Meigen, 1824)	5, 12, 33, 71	+	450-2350	ho	VI-IX	89
Syrphidae / 49						
<i>Epistrophe eligans</i> (Harris, 1780)	41		1000	et	VI	2
<i>Melisaeva cinctella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	41			ho	VI	2
<i>Eupeodes lapponicus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	41			h	V-VI	2
<i>Eupeodes corollae</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	8, 58	+	300-1000	ppta	IV-X	2
<i>Eupeodes luniger</i> (Meigen, 1822)	8	+	1000	ho	V-X	2
<i>Eupeodes nitens</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	41	+	1500	tp	VI-VIII	2
<i>Parasyrphus lineolus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	41	+	1500	h	VI	2
<i>Parasyrphus malinellus</i> (Collin, 1952)	41	+	1500	des	V-VI	2
<i>Scaeva pyrastris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	+	1000	ho	VI-X	2
<i>Sphaerophoria scripta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	+	1000	ho	V-X	2
<i>Syrphus ribesii</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8, 41	+	1000-1500	h	IV-X	2

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References	
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		Fenology
<i>Syrphus torvus</i> Osten-Sacken, 1875	41	+	1500	ho	V-X 2	
<i>Syrphus vitripennis</i> Meigen, 1822	41	+	1500	ho	IV-X 2	
<i>Baccha elongata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	41			h	V-X 2	
<i>Chrysotoxum festivum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	41	+	1500	po	V-VIII 2	
<i>Chrysotoxum vernale</i> Loew, 1841	9	+	1500	esca	V-VII 2	
<i>Melanostoma mellinum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	4, 58	+	300-1800	h	IV-X 2	
<i>Platycheirus albimanus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	5	+	1500	ho	VI-VIII 2	
<i>Platycheirus scutatus</i> (Meigen, 1822)	41			h	V-VII 2	
<i>Paragus tibialis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	41			ho	V-X 2	
<i>Heringia pubescens</i> (Delucchi & Pschorn-Walcher, 1955)	41			h	VI 2	
<i>Pipizella virens</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	4	+	1800	tp	V-VIII 2	
<i>Chamaesyphus scaevoides</i> (Fallén, 1817)	4	+	1810	des	V-VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia albitarsis</i> (Meigen, 1822)	9	+	1500	h	V-VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia antiqua</i> (Meigen, 1822)	5	+	1800	e, ? cse	V 2	
<i>Cheilosia bureschi</i> (Delkeskamp, 1942)	8	+	900-1000	Ebg	VII 41	
<i>Cheilosia carbonaria</i> Egger, 1860	41	+	1500	wces	VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia flavipes</i> (Panzer, 1798)	5	+	1500	wces	V-VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia frontalis</i> Loew, 1857	8	+	900-1000	e	V-VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia gagatea</i> Loew, 1857	6	+	1200-1400	cse	V-VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia impressa</i> Loew, 1840	8	+	900-1000	hoes	VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia montana</i> Egger, 1860	41	+	1500	wes	V-VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia mutabilis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	5	+	1500-2000	wcp	IV-VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia nebulosa</i> (Verrall, 1871)	5	+	1800	e	V-VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia proxima</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	41			hoes	V-VIII 2	
<i>Cheilosia pubera</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	41	+	1800	e	VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia ruralis</i> (Meigen, 1822)	5, 58	+	300-1800	hoes	IV-VI 2	
<i>Cheilosia sahilbergi</i> Becker, 1894	4	+	1810	e	V 2	
<i>Cheilosia variabilis</i> (Panzer, 1798)	41	+	1500	wcp	VI-VIII 2	
<i>Cheilosia velutina</i> Loew, 1840	41			hoes	VI-VIII 2	
<i>Cheilosia vernalis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	5	+	1800	hoes	V 2	

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Pipizella viduata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	10	+	1000-1500	e	V-VIII	2
<i>Lejogaster metalina</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	10	+	1000-1500	tp	V-VIII	2
<i>Lejogaster tarsata</i> (Meigen, 1822)	58		300-400	tp	VI-X	2
<i>Merodon ruficornis</i> Meigen, 1822	58		300-400	ena	V-VI	2
<i>Eristalis arbustorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	+	1000	ho	IV-X	2
<i>Myathropa florea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	+	1000	tp	IV-X	2
<i>Syrirta pipiens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	+	900-1000	sk	V-X	2
<i>Microdon mutabilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	9	+	1000-1600	hoes	V-VI	2
SCHIZOPHORA						
ACALYPTRATA						
Conopidae / 2		1				
<i>Physocephala pusilla</i> (Meigen, 1824)	58		300-400	wcp	VI-VII	44
<i>Myopa buccata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	4	+	1800	tp	V-VII	1
Tephritidae / 2		2				
<i>Actiura coryli</i> (Rossi, 1790)	8	+	900-1000	mwca	IV-VIII	45
<i>Oxyna nebulosa</i> (Wiedemann, 1817)	4	+	1800	eswa	V	45
Piophilidae / 1		1				
<i>Liopiophila varipes</i> (Meigen, 1830)	4	+	1800	h	VI-X	54
Chamaemyiidae / 12		4				
<i>Parochitiphilla (Euestelia) coronata</i> (Loew, 1858)	3, 34, 55	+	350-2350	tp	V-IX	19
<i>Chamaemyia aestiva</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1970	4, 37	+	1800-2200	tp	V-IX	18
<i>Chamaemyia aridella</i> (Fallén, 1823)	4, 38, 58, 71	+	300-2200	e	V-IX	18
<i>Chamaemyia bicolor</i> Beschovski, 1994	64			Ebg	VII	17
<i>Chamaemyia juncorum</i> (Fallén, 1823)	34, 36, 38, 56	+	350-2200	tp, ? hop	V-IX	18
<i>Chamaemyia polystigma</i> (Meigen, 1830)	34, 55		350-650	tp, ? hop	V-IX	18
<i>Chamaemyia subjuncorum</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1970	27		600-1000	? tp	V-VII	18
<i>Leucopis (Leucopis) aphidiperda</i> Rondani, 1847	33, 34, 58		300-650	esca	V-IX	19
<i>Leucopis (Leucopis) atritarsis</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1958	34		350-450	h	V-VIII	19
<i>Leucopis (Leucopis) glyphinivora</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1958	27, 34		350-700	ho	V-VIII	19
<i>Leucopis (Leucopis) pseudomelanopus</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1961	34		350-450	esca	V-VIII	19

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Leucopis (Leucopis) revisenda</i> Tanasijtshuk, 1970	34		350-450	esca	VIII	19
Sepsidae / 1		1				
<i>Sepsis fulgens</i> Meigen, 1826	4	+	1800	tp	V-IX	54
Agromyzidae / 15		15				
<i>Agromyza lithospermi</i> Spencer, 1963	8	+	900-1000	e		9
<i>Agromyza reptans</i> Fallén, 1823	8	+	900-1000	ho		9
<i>Amauromyza (Amauromyza) morionella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1848)	8	+	900-1000	ena		9
<i>Amauromyza (Cephalomyza) labiatarum</i> (Hendel, 1920)	8	+	900-1000	e		9
<i>Lirionomyza eupatorii</i> (Kaltenbach, 1873)	8	+	900-1000	h		9
<i>Pseudonapomyza europaea</i> Spencer, 1973	5	+	1800	h	VII-VIII	38
<i>Phytomyza alpina</i> Groschke, 1957	71	+	2000	h		9
<i>Phytomyza artemisivora</i> Spencer, 1971	8	+	900-1000	e		9
<i>Phytomyza chaerophylli</i> (Kaltenbach, 1856)	8	+	900-1000	e		9
<i>Phytomyza conyzae</i> Hendel, 1920	8	+	900-1000	wpo		9
<i>Phytomyza obscurella</i> Fallén, 1823	8	+	900-1000	e		9
<i>Phytomyza petoei</i> Hering, 1924	8	+	900-1000	po		9
<i>Phytomyza salviae</i> (Hering, 1924)	8	+	900-1000	e		9
<i>Phytomyza tussilaginis</i> Hendel, 1925	8	+	900-1000	e, ? h		9
<i>Chromatomyia saxifragae</i> (Hering, 1924)	71	+	2000	csee		9
Opomyzidae / 3		2				
<i>Opomyza florum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	5, 8, 34, 58	+	300-1800	e	V-XI	29
<i>Opomyza germinationis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	34, 58		300-450	h	VI-X	29
<i>Geomyza tripunctata</i> Fallén, 1823	5, 7, 9, 67, 77	+	1800-2575	h	V-X	29
Carnidae / 5		5				
<i>Meoneura alpina</i> Hennig, 1948	5	+	2000	csee	VII-VIII	20
<i>Meoneura flavifacies</i> Collin, 1930	5	+	2000	h	V-VII	20
<i>Meoneura flavifrons</i> Papp, 1981	3, 4, 37, 38, 66, 70, 72	+	1800-2700	e	V-IX	20
<i>Meoneura glaberrima</i> Becker, 1910	4, 33	+	450-1800	wp	V-X	20
<i>Meoneura graeca</i> Hennig, 1972	34	+	350-450	Eb	IV-X	20
Milichiidae / 4		1				

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Desmometopa sordida</i> (Fallén, 1820)	27		600-1000	ho	IV-VIII	20
<i>Leptomotopa niveipennis</i> (Strobl, 1900)	34, 55		350-650	wp	V-X	20
<i>Leptomotopa ruffifrons</i> Becker, 1903	34, 55		350-650	mca	V-IX	20
<i>Madiza glabra</i> Fallén, 1820	53	+	1000-1200	h	IV-X	20
Chloropidae / 72		48				
<i>Rhodesiella fedtschenkoi</i> Nartshuk, 1978	34		350-450	nemit	VIII	22, 24
<i>Aphanotrigonum femorellum</i> Collin, 1948	34		350-450	wp	V-X	22, 24
<i>Aphanotrigonum parahaastatum</i> Dely-Draskovits, 1981	34, 57		350-500	hom	VII-IX	22, 24
<i>Aphanotrigonum trilineatum</i> (Meigen, 1830)	27, 34, 51, 53, 57	+	350-1150	wces	IV-IX	22, 24
<i>Conioscinella frontella</i> (Fallén, 1820)	53, 69	+	1000-2200	hoes	VI-VIII	24
<i>Dicraeus (Dicraeus) ingratus</i> (Loew, 1866)	4	+	1800	h	V-VII	24
<i>Dicraeus (Dicraeus) nigropilosus</i> Becker, 1910	51, 53	+	1000-1100	eit	V-VII	24
<i>Dicraeus (Dicraeus) raptus</i> (Haldiday, 1838)	46, 51	+	1000-1250	e	IV-VII	24
<i>Dicraeus (Dicraeus) tibialis</i> (Macquart, 1835)	Predel		800-1000	ha	V-VII	24
<i>Elachiptera cornuta</i> (Fallén, 1820)	27, 51, 53		600-1100	hop	IV-VII	24
<i>Elachiptera submediterranea</i> Beschowski, 1980	59		1230	Eb	V-X	15, 24
<i>Elachiptera tuberculifera</i> (Corti, 1909)	8, 27, 53	+	600-1200	hop	IV-X	24
<i>Incertella albipalpis</i> (Meigen, 1830)	5, 28, 50, 53	+	600-1800	hoes	IV-X	24
<i>Lipara similis</i> Schiner, 1854	18		500-700	? wp	III-VI	24
<i>Microceris trigonella</i> (Duda, 1933)	33		450-650	wes	V-IX	24
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) alopecuri</i> Balachovsky & Mesnil, 1935	51, 53		850-1100	e	V-IX	22, 24
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) cariciphila</i> Collin, 1946	58, 70, 72	+	300-2700	wces	V-VIII	24
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) frit</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	4, 7, 9, 28, 33, 34, 35, 37, 38, 50, 53, 57, 62, 66, 69, 70, 72, 77	+	300-2700	hpta, k	IV-X	24
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) maura</i> (Fallén, 1820)	8, 34	+	350-1000	wes	V-X	24
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) nigerrima</i> (Macquart, 1835)	5, 9, 27, 35, 37, 38, 42, 50, 53, 54, 67, 71	+	700-2500	e	IV-X	24
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) nitidissima</i> (Meigen, 1838)	7, 34, 58	+	300-2100	h	IV-IX	24
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) phlei</i> Nartshuk, 1955	27, 70, 72	+	600-2500	e	IV-IX	22, 24
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) pusilla</i> (Meigen, 1830)	5, 7, 28, 37, 50, 53, 55, 59, 70, 72	+	600-2700	hop	IV-X	24
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) vastiator</i> (Curtis, 1845)	5, 28, 51, 53, 62	+	1000-1740	e	IV-X	24

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) ventricosi</i> Nartshuk, 1955	71	+	2200	e	IV-X	24
<i>Oscinomorpha arcuata</i> (Duda, 1932)	34, 47, 56, 58	+	300-1230	eswa	V-VIII	24
<i>Oscinomorpha minutissima</i> (Strobl, 1900)	5, 34, 51, 53, 57	+	350-2000	wp	V-VIII	24
<i>Oscinomorpha sordidissima</i> (Strobl, 1903)	50, 53	+	1000-1200	e	V-VIII	24
<i>Polydaspis ruficornis</i> (Macquart, 1835)	33, 58	+	300-650	po	V-X	24
<i>Rhopalopterus anthracinum</i> (Meigen, 1830)	33, 58	+	300-650	wces?	V- VIII	24
<i>Trachysiphonella pygmaea</i> (Meigen, 1838)	8, 34, 53, 58	+	300-1000	wes?	VI-X	22, 24
<i>Trachysiphonella ruficeps</i> (Macquart, 1835)	34, 57	+	350-500	e	V-X	24
<i>Trachysiphonella scutellata</i> von Roser, 1840	9, 53	+	900-1600	eca	V-X	24
<i>Tricimba (Nartshukiella) cincta</i> (Meigen, 1830)	8, 48, 50, 53, 58	+	300-1400	h	V-X	24
<i>Tricimba (Nartshukiella) humeralis</i> (Loew, 1858)	58	+	300-400	hop	IV-X	24
<i>Cetema (Cetema) cereris</i> (Fallén, 1820)	4, 8, 19, 50	+	700-1800	hoes	V-VIII	24
<i>Cetema (Cetema) elongatum</i> (Meigen, 1830)	51, 53, 58	+	300-1200	h	V-VIII	16, 24
<i>Cetema (Cetema) myopinum</i> (Loew, 1866)	8, 34, 57	+	350-1000	esca	VII-VIII	24
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) calceatus</i> Meigen, 1830	34, 51, 53, 56	+	350-1200	wces	V-IX	24
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) fasciatus</i> Meigen, 1830	43	+	1900	wces	VI-IX	24
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) finitimus</i> Becker, 1910	3, 5, 59	+	1230-2350	ewca	VI-VII	24
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) geminatus</i> Meigen, 1830	8, 5	+	1000-1900	wces	VI-VIII	14, 24
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) hypostigma</i> Meigen, 1830	8	+	900-1000	e	V-X	24
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) meigenii</i> Loew, 1866	8, 48	+	1000-1430	hoes	VI-X	24
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) ringens</i> Loew, 1866	53	+	1000-1200	wces	VII-X	24
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) scalaris</i> Meigen, 1830	8, 48	+	1000-1430	wces	IV-VII	24
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) speciosus</i> Meigen, 1830	4, 38, 50, 66, 69	+	1140-2500	wes	V-IX	24
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) troglodytes</i> (Zetterstedt, 1848)	5, 8, 42, 51, 71	+	1000-2000	wces	V-X	24
<i>Diplotoxa messoria</i> (Fallén, 1820)	19, 33, 50, 58, 59	+	300-1230	h	VI-X	24
<i>Elachiptereticus italicus</i> Duda, 1933	34	+	350	se	V	24
<i>Lasiosina albipila</i> (Loew, 1866)	34, 57	+	350-500	des?	VI-VII	24
<i>Lasiosina herpini</i> (Guérin-Ménéville, 1843)	27, 48, 53	+	600-1400	tp	IV-IX	24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) athletica</i> Fedoseeva, 1974	8, 53, 65	+	450-1200	csee	VI-IX	24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) bohemicana</i> Fedoseeva, 1962	34, 57	+	350-500	e	VII-VIII	24

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)		
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) femorata</i> Macquart, 1835	34, 53, 57	+	350-1200	e	VI-IX 24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) meigeni</i> Nartshuk, 2006	5	+	1600	wes	VII-IX 24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) nigriseta</i> Fedoseeva, 1960	51, 53	+	1100-1200	wces	VI-VII 24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) nigriventris</i> Macquart, 1835	5, 7, 31, 34, 53, 57	+	350-2200	h	IV-X 24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) pluriseta</i> Péterfi, 1961	53		1000-1200	wces	V-IX 24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) rohdendorfi</i> Fedoseeva, 1974	50		1140	e	VII-VIII 24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) rufa</i> Fedoseeva, 1962	34, 50, 57		350-1140	e	VI-VIII 24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) saltatrix</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	4, 7, 8, 48, 50, 51, 53, 59	+	950-2200	h	IV-X 24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) triangulina</i> Fedoseeva, 1960	8, 51, 53	+	950-1200	e	V-VII 24
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) zahvatkini</i> Fedoseeva, 1960	4, 8, 65	+	450-1800	des	VI-IX 24
<i>Paractephala longicornis</i> (Fallén, 1820)	34, 57		350-500	eswa	VII-X 24
<i>Phyladelphus thalhammeri</i> Becker, 1910	34, 57		350-500	e, ? cse	V-X 24
<i>Thaumatomyia elongatula</i> (Becker, 1910)	34, 57		350-500	e, ? cse	VIII 24
<i>Thaumatomyia glabra</i> (Meigen, 1830)	4, 9, 19, 48, 53	+	1000-1800	h	IV-X 24
<i>Thaumatomyia hallandica</i> Andersson, 1966	19, 34, 49, 57		350-1450	wces	V-VIII 24
<i>Thaumatomyia notata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	2, 28, 48, 50, 53	+	600-2200	ppt	IV-X 24
<i>Thaumatomyia rufa</i> (Macquart, 1835)	5	+	1500	hop	V-X 24
<i>Thaumatomyia sulcifrons</i> (Becker, 1907)	53, 27		600-1000	wcp	V-X 24
Sphaeroceridae / 2		1			
<i>Pseudocollinella humida</i> (Haliday, 1836)	41			pat	VIII 12
<i>Rachispoda lutosa</i> (Stenhammar, 1855)	26	+	2020-2392	h	V-VIII 12
Camillidae / 1		1			
<i>Camilla atrimana</i> Strobl, 1910	53	+	1000-1200	eswa	V-VI 13, 21
Diastatidae / 1		1			
<i>Diastata costata</i> Meigen, 1830	59	+	1230	e, ? h	V-X 21
Ephydriidae / 33		25			
<i>Psilopa nitidula</i> (Fallén, 1813)	5, 7, 48, 51, 53, 58, 67	+	300-2575	pat	IV-X 23, 30
<i>Psilopa obscuripes</i> Loew, 1860	5, 58	+	300-2000	wp	IV-X 23, 30
<i>Psilopa polita</i> (Macquart, 1835)	5, 7, 27, 38, 54, 59	+	600-2200	dp	IV-X 30

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Hydrelia griseola</i> (Fallén, 1813)	4, 7, 8, 19, 28, 50, 53, 66, 69, 71, 77	+	600-2500	sk	IV-IX	31
<i>Hydrelia maura</i> Meigen, 1838	66	+	2200-2500	wp	IV-X	23, 31
<i>Notiphila venusta</i> Loew, 1856	59	+	1230	dp	V-VIII	23, 31
<i>Notiphila graecula</i> Becker, 1926	59	+	1230	nemit	V-X	23, 31
<i>Notiphila nigricornis</i> Stenhammar, 1844	59	+	1230	wcp	V-IX	23, 31
<i>Athyroglossa nudiuscula</i> Loew, 1873	34, 56		350-650	cse, ? cse na	VII-VIII	23, 33
<i>Athyroglossa ordinata</i> Becker, 1896	34, 55		350-650	wp	IV-VIII	23, 33
<i>Allotrichoma laterale</i> (Loew, 1860)	34, 55		350-650	h	IV-X	33
<i>Dicrocerina obscurella</i> (Fallén, 1813)	58, 27		300-600	hnat	IV-X	23, 33
<i>Ditrichophora calceata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	19		700-750	ena	V-IX	23, 33
<i>Ditrichophora fuscella</i> (Stenhammar, 1844)	19, 59	+	700-1230	des, ? dp	IV-IX	23, 33
<i>Hecamedoides unispinosus</i> (Collin, 1943)	59	+	1230	hnat	IV-VIII	33
<i>Ilythea spilotata</i> (Curtis, 1832)	8	+	900-1000	h	IV-VIII	23
<i>Nostima picta</i> (Fallén, 1813)	54	+	2000-2190	hn	IV-X	23, 32
<i>Philygria posticata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	53	+	1000-1200	des	IV-IX	23, 32
<i>Philygria stictica</i> (Meigen, 1830)	2, 9, 28, 53	+	600-2100	e	IV-X	23, 32
<i>Philygria vittipennis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	5, 7, 38, 53, 71, 77	+	1000-2400	h	V-IX	23, 32
<i>Hyadina guttata</i> (Fallén, 1813)	27, 71, 77	+	600-2320	tp	V-X	23, 32
<i>Parydra</i> (<i>Chaetoapraea</i>) <i>fossarum</i> (Haliday, 1833)	8, 59	+	900-1230	h	IV-IX	23, 34
<i>Parydra</i> (<i>Parydra</i>) <i>coarctata</i> (Fallén, 1813)	18, 34		350-700	hop	IV-X	23, 34
<i>Parydra</i> (<i>Parydra</i>) <i>cognata</i> Loew, 1860	18, 34		350-700	wp	V-X	23, 34
<i>Scatophila caviceps</i> (Stenhammar, 1844)	27, 66	+	600-2500	hop	IV-X	23, 34
<i>Scatophila despecta</i> (Haliday, 1839)	66	+	2500	h	V-X	23, 34
<i>Scatophila farinae</i> Becker, 1903	58		300-400	hom	VIII-X	23, 34
<i>Linnellia quadrata</i> (Fallén, 1813)	53	+	1000-1200	h	IV-X	23, 34
<i>Lamproscatella bimaculata</i> Hendel, 1933	37, 66	+	2200-2500	h	VII-X	23, 34
<i>Lamproscatella sibilans</i> (Haliday, 1833)	27, 37, 53	+	600-2300	h	V-VII	23, 34
<i>Lamproscatella unipunctata</i> (Becker, 1907)	4, 53, 54, 66, 69, 71, 77	+	1000-2500	mca	IV-X	23, 34
<i>Scatella</i> (<i>Scatella</i>) <i>stagnalis</i> (Fallén, 1813)	59	+	1230	hpta	IV-X	23, 34

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Scatella (Scatella) tenuicosta</i> Collin, 1930	5, 27, 38, 53, 66, 69, 71, 77	+	600-2500	hat	IV-X	23, 34
CALYPTRATA						
Hippoboscidae / 1						
<i>Melophagus ovinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	5	+	1500-2000	k	VI-X	10
Anthomyiidae / 1						
<i>Delia radicum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	4	+	1810	h	V-VIII	54
Fanniidae / 6						
<i>Fannia canicularis</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	4, 9, 17, 23, 27, 53, 58, 70	+	300-2300	k	III-XI	54, 90
<i>Fannia incisurata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	4, 58	+	300-1810	hn	III-X	54, 90
<i>Fannia lepida</i> (Wiedemann, 1817)	4	+	1810	ho	IV-X	54
<i>Fannia manicata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	4	+	1810	ho	V-X	54
<i>Fannia monilis</i> (Haliday, 1838)	4	+	1810	wcp	IV-IX	54, 92
<i>Fannia scalaris</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	4, 9, 17, 23, 28, 34, 53, 58, 70	+	300-2500	hptn	II-X	54, 90
Muscidae / 49						
<i>Muscina levida</i> (Harris, 1780)	9, 17, 23, 27, 34, 53, 58, 70	+	300-2500	h	II-XI	90
<i>Muscina stabulans</i> (Fallén, 1817)	9, 17, 23, 28, 34, 53, 58, 71	+	300-2500	k	III-X	90
<i>Thricops cunctans</i> (Meigen, 1826)	41	+	1500-2000	hoes	VI-VII	92
<i>Thricops furcatus</i> (Stein, 1916)	9	+	1200	h	VII	92
<i>Thricops genarum</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	5	+	1300-1700	des	V-VIII	92
<i>Thricops longipes</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	41	+	900-2000	hoes	VI-VII	92
<i>Thricops nigritellus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	41	+	1200-2000	wes	VI-IX	92
<i>Thricops simplex</i> (Wiedemann, 1817)	41	+	200-1600	wp	V-X	92
<i>Hydrotaea armipes</i> (Fallén, 1825)	4, 17	+	1810-2500	ho	IV-IX	54, 90
<i>Hydrotaea dentipes</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	4	+	1810	hno	V-X	54
<i>Hydrotaea glabricula</i> (Fallén, 1825)	8	+	900	hop	VII-IX	92
<i>Hydrotaea ignava</i> (Harris, 1780)	53, 58	+	300-1200	ho	IV-X	90
<i>Hydrotaea irritans</i> (Fallén, 1823)	4, 53	+	1000-1810	tp	V-X	54, 90
<i>Hydrotaea meteorica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	4	+	1810	h	IV-IX	54, 92
<i>Hydrotaea similis</i> Meade, 1887	4	+	1810	tp	VI-X	54, 92
<i>Musca amita</i> Hennig, 1964	8, 17, 23, 28, 34, 53, 58	+	300-2500	hoes	VI-IX	90

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References	
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		Fenology
<i>Musca autumnalis</i> De Geer, 1776	7, 9, 23, 34, 53, 58	+	300-2400	hpt	IV-XI 90	
? <i>Musca bezzii</i> Patton & Cragg, 1913	28		1500	? dpo	VI-VIII 90	
<i>Musca domestica</i> Linnaeus, 1758	4, 9, 53, 58	+	300-1810	k	IV-XI 54, 90	
<i>Musca larvipara</i> Portschinsky, 1910	41	+	300-1300	wcp	IV-X 91	
<i>Musca tempestiva</i> Fallén, 1817	41	+	300-1200	ppt	V-IX 90	
<i>Musca vitripennis</i> Meigen, 1826	8, 17, 23, 28, 34, 53, 58, 71	+	300-2500	po	IV-XI 90	
<i>Morellia hortorum</i> (Fallén, 1817)	8, 53	+	900-1200	po	V-X 90	
<i>Morellia podagrica</i> (Loew, 1857)	4, 53	+	1000-1810	h	V-IX 54, 90	
<i>Morellia simplex</i> (Loew, 1857)	9, 53	+	900-1200	tp	IV-X 90	
<i>Neomyia cornicina</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	23, 53	+	900-1200	hnoa	IV-X 90	
<i>Pyrellia vivida</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	8, 17, 23, 28, 34, 53, 58	+	300-2500	po	V-IX 90	
<i>Dasyphora penicillata</i> (Egger, 1865)	5, 9, 17, 23, 28, 34, 53, 58, 71	+	300-2400	wp	II-X 54, 90	
<i>Dasyphora paratorum</i> (Meigen, 1826)	5, 9, 17, 23, 28, 53, 71	+	300-2400	wp	III-X 54, 90	
<i>Phaonia candicans</i> (Pandellé, 1898)	53	+	1000-1100	e	V-VI 92	
<i>Phaonia errans</i> (Meigen, 1826)	41	+	500-1200	h	V-IX 92	
<i>Phaonia fuscata</i> (Fallén, 1825)	53		1000	po	V-VI 90	
<i>Phaonia scutellata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	5	+	1500	ena	IV-X 92	
<i>Phaonia serva</i> (Meigen, 1826)	23, 71	+	900-2000	h	IV-VII 90, 92	
<i>Phaonia subventa</i> (Harris, 1780)	41	+	300-1900	ena	V-IX 92	
<i>Phaonia tuguriorum</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	8	+	900-1000	wcp	V-VIII 92	
<i>Helina confinis</i> (Fallén, 1825)	41	+	300-1800	des	VI-IX 92	
<i>Helina depuncta</i> (Fallén, 1825)	8, 53	+	900-1200	esca	IV-X 90, 92	
<i>Helina fratercula</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	9	+	900-1200	e	VII-VIII 92	
<i>Helina laxifrons</i> (Zetterstedt, 1860)	4	+	1810	h	VI 92	
<i>Mydaea corni</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	28	+	1500	hop	V-X 90	
<i>Mydaea electra</i> (Zetterstedt, 1860)	41	+	300-1000	h	VI-IX 92	
<i>Mydaea humeralis</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	41	+	300-1000	esca	VI-IX 92	
<i>Myospila mediotabunda</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	5, 53	+	1000-1800	hno	V-XI 54, 90	
<i>Hebecnema vespertina</i> (Fallén, 1823)	41	+	300-1500	h	V-IX 90, 92	
<i>Graphomya maculata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	8	+	900-1000	poa	IV-IX 90	

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Spilogona dispar</i> (Fallén, 1823)	41	+	300-2000	wes	V-X	92
<i>Linnophora maculosa</i> (Meigen, 1826)	41	+	300-1800	ewca	VII-IX	92
<i>Linnophora obsignata</i> (Rondani, 1866)	9	+	900-1000	wpat	VII-X	92
Calliphoridae / 3		3				
<i>Calliphora vicina</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	4	+	1810	k	II-XI	54
<i>Calliphora vomitoria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	4	+	1810	ha	IV-X	54
<i>Lucilia caesar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	4	+	1810	hop	IV-X	54
Sarcophagidae / 18		15				
<i>Blaesoxipha (Servaisia) erythrura</i> (Meigen 1826)	8	+	900-1000	eca	VI-VIII	102
<i>Ravinia pernix</i> (Harris, 1780)	5, 71	+	1810-2000	po	IV-X	54, 102
<i>Sarcophaga (Bellieriomima) subulata</i> Pandellé, 1896	8	+	900-1000	wes	VII	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) crassimargo</i> Pandellé, 1896	71	+	2000	wesca	VI-VII	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) maculata</i> Meigen, 1835	4	+	1810	sp. ? wcp	VI-VII	54
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) novercoides</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	71	+	2000	ena	VI-VII	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Myorhina) nigriventris</i> (Meigen, 1826)	71	+	2400	dp	VI-VII	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Myorhina) soerus</i> Rondani, 1860	71	+	1810	e	VI-IX	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Myorhina) soror</i> Rondani, 1860	71	+	1950-2200	e	VI-VII	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Sarcotachinella) sinuata</i> Meigen, 1826	4	+	1810	h	VI-VIII	46
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) mutila</i> Villeneuve, 1912	71	+	1950-2400	csee	VI-IX	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) porrecta</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	71	+	1950-2200	se	VI-VII	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) vicina</i> Macquart, 1835	71	+	1950-2400	e	VII	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteronychia) infantilis</i> Böttcher, 1913	71	+	1950-2200	e	VII-VIII	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Bercaea) africa</i> (Wiedemann, 1824)	58		300-400	hpt, ? hptn	IV-X	46
<i>Sarcophaga (Pandelleana) protuberans</i> Pandellé, 1896	34, 71	+	350-2200	wces, ? esca	VI-VII	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Parasarcophaga) hirtipes</i> (Wiedemann, 1830)	34		350-450	ptm	VII	102
<i>Sarcophaga (Sarcophaga) variegata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	34, 56		350-600	e	VII	102
Tachinidae / 203		147				
<i>Exorista (Exorista) larvarum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8, 33, 34, 57, 58	+	300-1000	hop	V-IX	71
<i>Exorista (Podotachina) sorbillans</i> (Wiedemann, 1830)	33, 50, 53		700-1200	sppta	V-VIII	71
<i>Exorista (Adenia) mimula</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 34, 47, 57, 68	+	350-1200	hop	V-VIII	71

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Exorista (Adenia) rustica</i> (Fallén, 1810)	33, 34, 46	+	350-1250	hop	VI-X	71
<i>Chetogena filipalpis</i> Rondani, 1859	40		850	nmt	V, VI-X	71
<i>Chetogena obliquata</i> (Fallén, 1810)	47, 68		900-1200	tp	V-VIII	71
<i>Parasetigena silvestris</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863)	28	+	1400	des	V-VII	71
<i>Phorocera assimilis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	9, 33, 50		500-1200	des	IV-VII	71
<i>Phorocera grandis</i> (Rondani, 1859)	45		550-650	dp	IV-VI	70, 71
<i>Phorocera obscura</i> (Fallén, 1810)	9, 35, 47	+	700-1300	des	V-VII	71
<i>Bessa selecta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 34		350-750	hoes	V-IX	71
<i>Belida angelicae</i> (Meigen, 1824)	39		1250	wcp	V-VIII	71
<i>Meigenia dorsalis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	34, 47, 57	+	350-1300	hoes	V-X	71
<i>Meigenia mutabilis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	9, 24, 33, 34, 43, 52, 58	+	300-2400	wcp	IV-X	71
<i>Zaira cinerea</i> (Fallén, 1810)	34, 47, 50, 58, 68	+	300-1300	tp	V-VIII	71
<i>Medina collaris</i> (Fallén, 1820)	33, 68		700-900	hoes	V-VIII	70, 71
<i>Medina luctuosa</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 47	+	700-1300	hoes	V-IX	71
<i>Lecanipa bicincta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	64		800-1300	wces	VI-VIII	71
<i>Admontia podomyia</i> Brauer & Bergenstamm, 1889	20, 24, 25	+	2000-2300	e, bm	V-VIII	68, 71
<i>Oswaldia muscaria</i> (Fallén, 1810)	46	+	1250	des	V-VI	71
<i>Oswaldia spectabilis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	46, 51, 68	+	850-1250	e	VI-VIII	71
<i>Lomachantha parva</i> Rondani, 1859	46, 48, 50	+	1100-1400	et	V-VIII	71
<i>Erynniopsis antennata</i> (Rondani, 1861)	34, 58		300-450	? hom, h*	IV-IX	71
<i>Blondelia nigripes</i> (Fallén, 1810)	24, 33, 34, 45, 46, 57, 58, 69, 73	+	300-2400	tp, h*	V-X	71
<i>Compilurina concinnata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	9, 33, 45, 53, 58, 64, 73	+	300-1300	hoes, h*	IV-IX	71
<i>Vibrissina turrata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	9, 50	+	1000-1400	dp	V-VII	71
<i>Acernya acuticornis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	47, 68	+	900-1200	ess	VI-VIII	71
<i>Smidtia amoena</i> (Meigen, 1824)	34, 47	+	450-1230	hoes	V-VI	71
<i>Winthemia quadripustulata</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	34, 47, 68	+	350-1300	h	V-X	71
<i>Nemorilla floralis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	45, 58		300-650	hop	V-X	71
<i>Aplomya confinis</i> (Fallén, 1820)	47, 57, 68	+	500-1350	hop	V-IX	71
<i>Phebellia nigripalpis</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1847)	34, 48, 68	+	400-1400	des	V-VIII	71
<i>Tlephusa cinctima</i> (Rondani, 1859)	27, 29		700-900	ess	VI-VIII	71

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeo-		
				graphical		
<i>Epicampocera succincta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	28, 33	+	700-1500	tp	V-IX	71
<i>Phryxe nemea</i> (Meigen, 1824)	9, 33, 34, 40, 50, 64, 70	+	400-1950	hoes	V-X	71
<i>Phryxe prima</i> (Brauer & Bergenstamm, 1889)	74		700-750	mt	V-VII	71
<i>Phryxe vulgaris</i> (Fallén, 1810)	13, 45, 46, 57, 68	+	350-2000	h	V-X	70, 71
<i>Pseudoperichaeta nigrolineata</i> (Walker, 1853)	9, 27, 40	+	700-1450	des	V-VIII	71
<i>Lydella stabulans</i> (Meigen, 1824)	45, 73		500-700	wes	V-IX	70, 71
<i>Cadurciella tritaeniata</i> (Rondani, 1859)	33		450-700	des	V-VI	71
<i>Drino atropivora</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	34, 45, 47, 58, 68, 73	+	300-1300	sp	V-VIII	71
<i>Drino inconspicua</i> (Meigen, 1830)	6	+	1200-1300	wces	V-X	71
<i>Drino lota</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 40, 47	+	700-1300	pat	VI-IX	71
<i>Drino vicina</i> (Zetterstedt, 1849)	6, 8, 40, 64	+	500-1300	wces	VI-VIII	71
<i>Huebneria affinis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	19, 24, 33, 40	+	450-2400	ess	IV-X	71
<i>Carcelia (Carcelia) bombylans</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	15	+	1750-1800	des	V-VI	71
<i>Carcelia (Carcelia) gnava</i> (Meigen, 1824)	8, 27, 64	+	700-1000	des	V-VIII	71
<i>Carcelia (Carcelia) lucorum</i> (Meigen, 1824)	40, 45, 47	+	600-1300	tp	V-X	71
<i>Erycia festinans</i> (Meigen, 1824)	35, 47, 68	+	800-1300	wces	V-VIII	71
<i>Alsomyia capillata</i> (Rondani, 1859)	33, 40, 68		500-1000	hom	V-VIII	71
<i>Platymya fimbriata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	20, 24, 69	+	2000-2500	tp, bm	V-IX	68, 71
<i>Eumea linearicornis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	15, 40	+	700-1300	hoes	V-IX	71
<i>Clemelis pullata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	20, 22, 26, 33, 68, 69	+	500-2400	wcp	V-IX	71
<i>Pales pavida</i> (Meigen, 1824)	8, 23, 34, 45, 47, 65, 73	+	400-1300	hop	V-X	71
<i>Pales pumicata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 34		350-700	nm	V-VIII	71
<i>Phryno vetula</i> (Meigen, 1824)	45, 73		500-700	des	V-VI	71
<i>Bothria frontosa</i> (Meigen, 1824)	48, 51, 68	+	900-1300	hoes	IV-VII	71
<i>Allophorocera ferruginosa</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 42, 46, 68, 70, 75	+	700-1950	hoes	V-IX	71
<i>Allophorocera pachystyla</i> (Macquart, 1850)	43	+	2000	e, m	VII-VIII	71
<i>Eurysthaea scutellaris</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1848)	33, 34, 45, 58		350-700	e	VI-VII	71
<i>Elodia ambulatoria</i> (Meigen, 1824)	47, 60	+	700-1300	wcp	V-VII	71
<i>Sturmia bella</i> (Meigen, 1824)	8, 34, 40, 48, 50, 57, 64	+	400-1400	po	V-IX	71
<i>Blepharipa pratensis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 46, 48, 58, 68	+	350-1400	tp, h*	V-VII	71

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Masicera pavoniae</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	19, 29, 31, 34, 64	+	400-1000	wp	V-VII	71
<i>Masicera silvatica</i> (Fallén, 1810)	45, 46, 50, 58, 68	+	350-1250	e	V-VIII	71
<i>Prosopea nigricans</i> (Egger, 1861)	39, 53, 58	+	350-1300	wcp	V-VIII	71
<i>Gaedia connexa</i> (Meigen, 1824)	8, 28, 33, 68	+	700-1400	e	V-IX	71
<i>Gaedia distincta</i> Egger, 1861	39, 68	+	900-1350	ess	VI-VIII	71
<i>Baumhaueria goniaeformis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	47, 68	+	900-1350	wp	III-VI	71
<i>Gonia bimaculata</i> Wiedemann, 1819	40, 45, 58		350-900	atm	III-IX	71
<i>Gonia capitata</i> (De Geer, 1776)	9, 13, 20, 27, 47, 50, 76	+	700-2000	wcp	V-VIII	71
<i>Gonia ornata</i> Meigen, 1826	34, 58		300-450	wcp	III-V	71
<i>Gonia picea</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	34, 45		350-650	wcp	III-VI	71
<i>Pseudogonia parisiaca</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1851)	33, 40, 47, 57, 58	+	300-1300	ess	VI-VX	71
<i>Pseudogonia ruffifrons</i> (Wiedemann, 1830)	31, 34		350-700	ppta	V-IX	71
<i>Spallanzania hebes</i> (Fallén, 1820)	31, 33, 58		300-700	ho	V-IX	71
<i>Tachina (Tachina) grossa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	19, 33, 34, 35, 45, 47, 48, 51, 68	+	350-1400	hoes	V-VIII	71
<i>Tachina (Tachina) magna</i> (Giglio-Tos, 1890)	34, 45, 58		300-650	sess	V-VII	71
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) casta</i> (Rondani, 1859)	30, 34		350-600	nm	IX-X	71
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) fera</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	20, 33, 40, 43, 47, 48, 51, 55, 58, 65, 68, 75, 76	+	300-1900	hop	V-X	71
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) magnicornis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	20, 22, 29, 33, 34, 42, 46, 48, 51, 55, 58, 68, 76	+	300-1900	hop	V-X	71
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) nupta</i> (Rondani, 1859)	22, 23, 33, 43, 58	+	300-1750	tp	V-IX	71
<i>Tachina (Servillia) lurida</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	34, 45, 57, 58		300-600	wp	III-VI	71
<i>Tachina (Echinogaster) praeceps</i> Meigen, 1824	34, 40, 47, 51, 57, 68	+	350-1300	wp	V-IX	71
<i>Nowickia (Nowickia) marklini</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	5, 11, 13, 16, 20, 47, 75	+	1250-2300	h, ? bm	VII-VIII	71
<i>Nowickia (Fabriciella) atripalpis</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863)	4, 12, 20, 43, 47, 69, 71, 76	+	1250-2250	hoes, bm	VII-IX	71
<i>Nowickia (Fabriciella) ferox</i> (Panzer, 1809)	13, 36, 47, 63, 68, 75	+	900-2300	wes	VI-IX	71
<i>Nowickia (Fabriciella) rondanii</i> (Giglio-Tos, 1890)	28, 33, 46, 68	+	700-1600	sess	IV-VIII	71
<i>Cnephatoachina damilevskiyi</i> (Portshinsky, 1882)	8, 27, 34, 35, 40, 68	+	350-950	mca	IV-VIII	68, 71
<i>Peleteria abdominalis</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	9, 40, 46, 48, 51	+	600-1300	nm	VI	71
<i>Peleteria ferrina</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	8, 23, 45, 50	+	600-1300	hoes	V-VIII	71

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Peleteria rubescens</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	10, 20, 29, 33, 34, 40, 47, 49, 51, 55, 58, 59, 75	+	300-2000	tp	V-IX 71
<i>Peleteria ruficornis</i> (Macquart, 1835)	34, 57		350-500	msws	VI-IX 71
<i>Peleteria varia</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	33, 34, 40, 47, 48, 50, 53, 57, 58, 68	+	300-1400	ppta	VII-IX 71
<i>Germania ruficeps</i> (Fallén, 1820)	35, 47, 50	+	700-1300	wcp	VI-VIII 71
<i>Nemoraea pellicuda</i> (Meigen, 1824)	9, 34, 41, 44, 48	+	350-1500	tp	V-IX 71
<i>Linnaemya</i> (<i>Linnaemya</i>) <i>comita</i> (Fallén, 1810)	8, 33, 34, 35, 39, 47, 57, 68	+	400-1300	ho	VI-IX 71
<i>Linnaemya</i> (<i>Bonellimyia</i>) <i>impudica</i> (Rondani, 1859)	8, 34, 45, 46, 51, 53	+	350-1300	cse	V-VIII 71
<i>Linnaemya</i> (<i>Ophina</i>) <i>haemorrhoidalis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	8, 13, 23, 28, 29, 32, 33, 35, 39, 42, 65, 68, 76	+	500-1850	hoes, bm	V-VIII 71
<i>Linnaemya</i> (<i>Ophina</i>) <i>helvetica</i> Herting, 1963	40, 68		700-900	cse	VI 71
<i>Linnaemya</i> (<i>Ophina</i>) <i>olsuffevi</i> Zimin, 1954	33, 68		600-900	hoes	VI-VII 70, 71
<i>Linnaemya</i> (<i>Ophina</i>) <i>picta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	39, 45, 47, 51, 57, 68	+	500-1300	po	VI-X 71
<i>Linnaemya</i> (<i>Ophina</i>) <i>rossica</i> Zimin, 1954	10, 33, 47, 49, 50, 76	+	700-1800	hoes	V-IX 71
<i>Linnaemya</i> (<i>Homoeonychia</i>) <i>lithiophaga</i> (Rondani, 1859)	33, 34		350-700	hom	V, IX 71
<i>Ernestia laevigata</i> (Meigen, 1838)	9, 48, 68	+	900-1430	hoes	V-IV 71
<i>Ernestia rudis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	8, 19, 21, 53, 76	+	750-1800	tp	V-VII 71
<i>Eurithia anthophila</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	10, 18, 68	+	700-1500	h	VIII-IX 71
<i>Eurithia caesia</i> (Fallén, 1810)	5, 22, 42	+	900-1640	hoes	VI-VIII 71
<i>Eurithia consobrina</i> (Meigen, 1824)	39		1200-1400	hoes	VII-VIII 71
<i>Hyalurgus lucidus</i> (Meigen, 1824)	28, 76	+	1400-1800	wces, bm	VI-VIII 71
<i>Zophomyia tenuula</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	8, 13, 23, 27, 29, 33, 35, 39, 41, 47, 75	+	400-1750	tp	V-VII 71
<i>Cleonice callida</i> (Meigen, 1824)	19, 68		700-900	des	V-VII 71
<i>Loewia brevifrons</i> (Rondani, 1856)	9, 33, 47, 51, 58, 68	+	300-1200	nm	VI-IX 71
<i>Loewia phaeoptera</i> (Meigen, 1824)	35, 45, 68		500-900	e	V-VIII 71
<i>Pseudopachystylum gonioides</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	15, 20, 68, 75	+	900-1800	hoes	V-VII 71
<i>Pelatachima tibialis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	34, 45, 47, 57	+	450-1300	hoes	IV-VIII 71
<i>Macquartia chalconota</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 46	+	500-1300	wes	VI-VII 71
<i>Macquartia dispar</i> (Fallén, 1820)	9, 40, 49, 50, 56	+	500-1400	ess	V-IX 71

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Macquartia grisea</i> (Fallén, 1810)	33, 35		500-800	e	V-X	71
<i>Macquartia praefica</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 34, 47, 55, 58, 59	+	300-1250	hom	V-VIII	68, 71
<i>Macquartia tenebricosa</i> (Meigen, 1824)	28, 33, 47, 58, 75	+	300-1800	wcp	V-X	71
<i>Phylomyptera cingulata</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	34, 58		300-400	e	V-IX	71
<i>Actia crassicornis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	28, 32, 35, 39	+	800-1500	ess	V-IX	71
<i>Actia pilipennis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	33, 58		300-700	hoes	VI-X	71
<i>Peribaea tibialis</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1851)	8, 34, 53	+	300-1000	spat	V-X	71
<i>Siphona cristata</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	8, 27, 34, 45, 53	+	350-1000	h	VI-VIII	71
<i>Siphona flavifrons</i> Staeger, 1849	20, 75	+	1700-1900	des, h*	VII-IX	71
<i>Siphona geniculata</i> (De Geer, 1776)	22, 23, 47	+	800-1300	hoes, h*	V-X	71
<i>Aphria longirostris</i> (Meigen, 1824)	10, 20, 34, 69, 70	+	350-2300	wcp	VI-X	71
<i>Demoticus plebejus</i> (Fallén, 1810)	47, 53, 70	+	1000-1950	wes	VI-VIII	71
<i>Bithia glirina</i> (Rondani, 1861)	9, 34, 40, 48	+	350-1450	wes	VI-IX	71
<i>Bithia modesta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	40, 45, 47, 59, 68	+	300-1200	hom	VI-VIII	71
<i>Leskia aurea</i> (Fallén, 1820)	23, 31, 68		700-900	hoes	V-VIII	71
<i>Mintho rufiventris</i> (Fallén, 1817)	8, 22, 29, 34, 45, 50	+	350-1000	tp	V-IX	71
<i>Microphthalma europaea</i> Egger, 1860	18, 68		700-900	? om	VI-VIII	71
<i>Dexiosoma caninum</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	47, 51	+	1100-1300	des	VI-IX	71
<i>Billaea fortis</i> (Rondani, 1862)	29, 31, 32, 45		650-800	des	V-VI	71
<i>Billaea pectinata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	27, 33, 34, 35, 39, 46, 50	+	350-1250	mca	V-VIII	71
<i>Billaea triangulifera</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	9, 15, 48, 51, 53	+	1100-1700	hoes	V-IX	71
<i>Dinera carinifrons</i> (Fallén, 1817)	8, 17, 20, 24, 33, 34, 45, 47, 51, 58, 69, 71, 76	+	300-2400	hoes	V-IX	71
<i>Dinera ferina</i> (Fallén, 1817)	8, 28, 33, 45, 47, 51, 57, 64	+	500-1600	wes	VI-VIII	71
<i>Estheria bohemani</i> (Rondani, 1862)	4, 50, 53, 62, 75	+	1000-1800	e	VII-VIII	67, 71
<i>Estheria petiolata</i> (Bonsdorff, 1866)	13, 20, 27, 33, 34, 47, 68, 76	+	400-1900	wces	V-VIII	71
<i>Estheria picta</i> (Meigen, 1826)	13, 28, 35, 40, 42, 45, 47, 48, 49, 58	+	300-1800	wcp	IV-IX	71
<i>Dexia rustica</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	8, 34, 45, 51	+	350-1000	hoes	V-IX	71
<i>Proserna siberita</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	4, 10, 15, 21, 33, 41, 42, 75	+	500-1800	hpta	VI-IX	71
<i>Zeuxia cinerea</i> Meigen, 1826	10, 20, 39, 42, 48, 50, 56	+	500-1900	wp	IV-IX	71

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Eriothrix apenninus</i> (Rondani, 1862)	20, 24, 36, 39, 42, 51, 62, 68, 69	+	900-2450	wp	VI-VIII	71
<i>Eriothrix rufomaculatus</i> (De Geer, 1776)	8, 24, 34, 43, 45, 52, 53	+	350-2450	tp	V-IX	71
<i>Ramonda spathulata</i> (Fallén, 1820)	34, 39, 48, 50	+	400-1350	tp	V-X	71
<i>Perisepsia carbonaria</i> (Panzer, 1798)	33, 34, 57		350-700	ppt	V-X	71
<i>Athrycia impressa</i> (Wulp, 1869)	39	+	1300	ess	VI-VIII	71
<i>Athrycia trepida</i> (Meigen, 1824)	8, 34, 47, 50, 68	+	350-1200	tp	V-VIII	68, 71
<i>Voria ruralis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	8, 13, 28, 33, 51	+	700-1800	k	VI-X	71
<i>Hyleorus elatus</i> (Meigen, 1838)	34, 40, 47, 53	+	350-1300	hoes	V-VIII	71
<i>Phyllomyia volvulus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	19, 28, 33, 62, 68, 74, 75	+	450-1750	hoes	V-VIII	71
<i>Thelaina nigripes</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	8, 34, 45, 47, 49, 57, 68	+	350-1300	tp	V-VIII	71
<i>Halidaya aurea</i> Egger, 1856	34, 68		350-900	hoes	VI-X	71
<i>Stomina caltindrata</i> (Rondani, 1862)	8, 34, 53	+	350-1000	mca	VI-IX	71
<i>Stomina tachinoides</i> (Fallén, 1817)	23, 34, 68	+	350-950	wcp	VI-X	71
<i>Rhamphina pedemontana</i> (Meigen, 1824)	21	+	1800	se, ? nm	VI-IX	71
<i>Dufouria chalybeata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	9, 34, 39	+	350-1300	dp	V-VII	71
<i>Dufouria nigrita</i> (Fallén, 1810)	8, 23, 45, 53, 57, 68	+	500-950	wcp	IV-VII	71
<i>Chetoptilia puella</i> (Rondani, 1862)	35, 57, 68		600-900	des	VI-IX	71
<i>Eliozeta helluo</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	30, 31, 33, 34, 45, 57, 58, 65		300-700	tp	V-IX	71
<i>Eliozeta pellucens</i> (Fallén, 1820)	8, 27, 34, 53, 59, 68	+	300-1000	des	V-VIII	71
<i>Chytiomyia continua</i> (Panzer, 1798)	34, 39, 40, 50, 57, 65	+	350-1300	tp	V-VIII	71
<i>Ectophasia crassipennis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	33, 34, 39, 53, 55, 57, 58, 60, 62, 75	+	300-1700	tp	V-IX	69, 71
<i>Ectophasia leucoptera</i> (Rondani, 1865)	34, 58		300-450	nmt	V-IV	69, 71
<i>Ectophasia oblonga</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	33, 45, 51, 53, 56, 58, 68	+	300-1200	wp	V-IX	71
<i>Gymnosoma clavatum</i> (Rohdendorf, 1947)	12, 28, 31, 33, 34, 40, 58, 68	+	350-1700	tp	V-VIII	71
<i>Gymnosoma costatum</i> (Panzer, 1800)	8, 29, 45, 58, 68	+	350-1000	tp	V-VII	71
<i>Gymnosoma desertorum</i> (Rohdendorf, 1947)	9, 23, 46, 51, 57, 58	+	350-1250	eecc	V-X	71
<i>Gymnosoma dolycoridis</i> Dupuis, 1961	33, 34, 46	+	350-1250	ess	V-IX	71
<i>Gymnosoma inornatum</i> Zimin, 1966	19, 46, 58	+	350-1250	tp	V-IX	71
<i>Gymnosoma nitens</i> Meigen, 1824	10, 39, 40, 49, 50, 64, 68	+	650-1400	esca	V-IX	71
<i>Gymnosoma nudifrons</i> Herting, 1966	8, 23, 27, 33, 47, 53	+	650-1300	hoes	V-VII	71

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Pirin	NP	Vertical (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Gymnosoma rotundatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8, 21, 28, 33, 34, 39, 42, 43, 46, 53, 57, 73, 74	+	350-1800	tp	V-IX	71
<i>Cistogaster globosa</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	34, 58		300-450	ess	VI-VIII	71
<i>Opesia cana</i> (Meigen, 1824)	34, 56, 57, 68		350-900	ess	VIII-IX	70, 71
<i>Elomya lateralis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	23, 28, 34, 40, 45, 46, 53	+	350-1400	tp	V-VII	71
<i>Phasia (Phasia) obesa</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	12, 28, 29, 32, 35, 39, 41, 47, 48, 50, 53, 68	+	750-1550	tp	V-X	71
<i>Phasia (Phasia) subcoleoprata</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	8, 23, 33, 47, 68	+	700-1300	tp	VI-X	71
<i>Phasia (Hyalomya) pusilla</i> Meigen, 1824	8, 33, 34, 45, 68	+	350-1000	tp	IV-X	71
<i>Strongygaster globula</i> (Meigen, 1824)	55, 68		500-950	hoes	VI-VII	71
<i>Dionaea aurifrons</i> (Meigen, 1824)	23, 33, 46, 53, 58	+	300-1250	tp	V-IX	71
<i>Leucostoma anthracinum</i> (Meigen, 1824)	34, 56, 58		300-550	wces	V-VII	68, 71
<i>Leucostoma tetraptera</i> (Meigen, 1824)	34, 39, 45, 50, 53	+	350-1250	wcp	VI-VIII	71
<i>Clairvillia biguttata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	29, 33, 34, 68		350-950	dp	V-VIII	71
<i>Labigastera forcipata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	9, 19, 23, 47, 68	+	700-1300	wes	VI-VIII	71
<i>Labigastera pauciseta</i> (Rondani, 1861)	8, 34, 39	+	350-1250	e, cse	VI-VIII	71
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) bicolor</i> (Olivier, 1812)	9, 30, 31, 33, 34, 35, 45, 46, 49, 53, 64, 68	+	300-1400	mca	V-VIII	71
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) brassicaria</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	21, 28, 34, 39, 44, 45, 47, 55, 60, 64, 73, 76	+	350-1800	hop	VI-IX	71
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) brevicornis</i> (Loew, 1844)	34, 47, 68	+	380-1300	des	V-VIII	71
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) pilipes</i> (Loew, 1844)	18, 23, 29, 35, 40		500-900	wcp	V-IX	71
<i>Cylindromyia (Dupuisia) crassa</i> (Loew, 1845)	34, 59, 68		350-950	mss	V-VIII	71
<i>Cylindromyia (Calocyptera) intermedia</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 45, 47	+	450-1250	h	V-VIII	71
<i>Cylindromyia (Neocyptera) auriceps</i> (Meigen, 1838)	8, 34	+	350-1000	tp	VI-IX	71
<i>Cylindromyia (Neocyptera) interrupta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	8, 18, 29, 46, 50, 53	+	500-1250	h	V-IX	71
<i>Hemyda vittata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	31, 40, 57		600-700	hoes	VI-VIII	71
<i>Besseria dimidiata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	19, 33		700-800	e	VI-VIII	71
<i>Besseria lateritia</i> (Meigen, 1824)	33, 58		300-600	? mt	V-VII	71
<i>Phania funesta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	34, 55, 57, 68		450-950	e	V-VIII	71

the fragmentary data for most families do not allow explicit conclusions about the adherence of the taxa to one or another vegetation zone to be made. The distribution of species in groups according to their presence in the vegetation belts has a relative character and depends on the specific features of taxa and research area as well as the duration of the research. There is a correlation between the horizontal and vertical distribution of Diptera. Species found above 2200–2500 m, most often have large areas – Cosmopolitan, Holarctic, Palaearctic, Eurosiberian or European distribution (Table 2).

The zoogeographical categorization of the species (Table 2) was made on the basis of current data about their distribution. Thus the tachinids are divided into 72 zoogeographical categories, combined into 2 main groups and 6 subgroups (Table 3).

Species distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it. This group (160 species – 21.6%) includes 27 categories, of which 22 combine species of northern type (widely distributed in Holarctic and Palaearctic) and 5 – species of southern type (distributed only in the southern parts of the Palaearctic). The difference between the separate vegetation belts with respect to this group is from 1.2% to 13.7% (from 3 to 87 species). In the first 4 vegetation belts the difference is minimal (not exceeding 5.0%) and increases in the sub-alpine and alpine belts where the species with vast areas dominate. It is very likely the establishment of other species of the group of northern type in the last 2 vegetation belts of Pirin Mt. in view of their distribution and poor study level of the higher parts of the mountain. It is accepted that the species of northern type have vast areas and ecological flexibility. In the superpalaearctic complex, the Holarctic species (76 species – 10.3%) prevail and from the other areographical categories the Holarctic-Oriental and the Palaearctic-Oriental forms are better presented (Table 3). The species of southern type are presented in the first 3 vegetation belts. Usually the scrutinized areographical complex is scanty presented and is not determinant for the zoogeographical characteristic of taxa in the Bulgarian fauna. In a highly mobile forms (such as Diptera) the complex is better presented and can reach 15–20%. In two-winged insects significant numbers of synanthropic and synovil forms with cosmopolitan distribution occur. They have anthropogenic areas, structured with the development of human civilization (before the beginning of contemporary investigations).

Species distributed only in the Palaearctic, but in more than one subregion (Palaearctic type). Taxa, whose areas include more than one Palaearctic

subregion in latitudinal direction, belong to this group. They are well represented in the high mobile groups and comprise about 25–35% of the species composition. A total of 196 species (26.5%) from this group, combined into 15 zoogeographical categories, has been established in the Pirin Mt. (Table 3). Its character is determined by the Transpalaearctic (58 species – 7.8%), West and Central Palaearctic (26 species – 3.4%) and West Palaearctic (25 species – 3.4%) species which are the most numerous. The correlation of these categories remains the same in the separate vegetation belts of Pirin Mt. with small deviations, and ranges from 3.1% to 11.7% (3 to 41 species). The Holopalaearctic, European-North African and Eurosiberian-Central Asian species are well presented. Twelve species have a longitudinal disjunction of the areas in regard to Siberia and Central Asia (Table 2 and Table 3). Probably some of these species are presented with sparse populations and will be specified under further investigations. Most often a latitudinal disjunction of the areas of this group lacks (GORODKOV, 1984; JOSIFOV, 1988). A significant portion of the species with wide vertical distribution (about 25%) belong to this group. It includes from 10.0% to 38.1% (1 to 116 species) of the species composition in the separate vegetation belts (Table 3). The vast areas and wide vertical distribution of the taxa of this group are an indication of the greater ecological flexibility of its species.

Species distributed within one subregion of the Palaearctic. This group (370 species – 50.0%) includes species with Eurosiberian (328 species – 44.3%) and Mediterranean (42 species – 5.7%) type of distribution (Table 3). The Mediterranean-Central Asian species are also included here according to KRYZHANOVSKY (1965) and LOPATIN (1989) who combine the Mediterranean and Central Asian subregions. The species with Mediterranean type of distribution are accepted in a general way and include faunistic elements (Submediterranean, Subiranian and Pontian) that could be considered separately as well (GRUEV & KUSMANOV 1994, 1999; GRUEV 1995, 2000d).

The Eurosiberian species include 10 areographical categories, of which the European (137 species – 18.5%), Holoeurosiberian (53 species – 7.2%) and Disjunct Eurosiberian (38 species – 5.1%) species are best represented. The ratio of these categories is different for the separate families (most numerous are the Holoeurosiberian species of the Tachinidae family as the Eurosiberian forms are 48% in total, while in other families the Central and South European species are better rep-

Table 3. Zoogeographical characteristic of the Pirin Diptera

Zoogeographical categories	Total number	Percentage	Vegetation belts					
			Xerothermic oak forests – up to 600-700 m	Mesophyllic and xeromesophyllic oak-hornbeam forests – from 600-700 m to 900-1000 m	Beech forests - from 900-1000 to 1500-1600 m	Coniferous forests – from 1300-1600 m to 2000-2200 m	Subalpine vegetation – from 2200 m to 2500 m	Alpine vegetation – over 2500 m
Species distributed in the Palearctic and out of it	160	21.6	55 (21.4)	81 (22.2)	89 (22.3)	69 (26.4)	27 (35.1)	3 (30.0)
NORTH TYPE	155	20.9	52 (20.2)	78 (21.4)	87 (22.1)	69 (26.4)	27 (35.1)	3 (30.0)
Cosmopolitan (k)	6	0.8	4	4	5	6	2	
Semicosmopolitan (sk)	2	0.3	1	2	2	1	1	
Holarctic-Paleotropical-Neotropical (hptn)	2	0.3	2	1	1	1	1	
Holarctic-Paleotropical-Australian (hpta)	3	0.4	2	2	3	2	1	1
Holarctic-Paleotropical (hpt)	1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	
Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental-Australian (hnoa)	1	0.1		1	1			
Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental (hno)	4	0.5		1	1	4	2	
Holarctic-Neotropical-Afrotropical (hnat)	2	0.3	1		1			
Holarctic-Neotropical (hn)	2	0.3	1	1	1	1	1	
Holarctic-Afrotropical (hat)	1	0.1	1	1	1	1	1	
Holarctic-Oriental (ho)	25	3.4	6	13	14	8	3	
Holarctic-Australian (ha)	2	0.3		1		1		
Palearctic-Paleotropical-Australian (ppta)	3	0.4	3	3	1			
Palearctic-Oriental-Australian (poa)	1	0.1		1				
Palearctic-Paleotropical (ppt)	4	0.5	3	2	2	2	1	
Palearctic-Afrotropical (pat)	3	0.4	1	2	2	1	1	1
Palearctic-Oriental (po)	13	1.8	5	8	9	5	2	
Palearctic-Australian (pa)	1	0.1				1	1	
West Palearctic-Oriental (wpo)	1	0.1		1				
Disjunct Palearctic-Oriental (dpo)	1	0.1			1			
West Palearctic-Afrotropical (wpat)	1	0.1		1				
Holarctic (h)	76	10.3	21	32	41	34	10	1
SOUTH TYPE	5	0.7	3 (1.2)	3 (0.8)	2 (0.5)			
South Palearctic-Paleotropical-Australian (sppta)	1	0.1		1	1			
South Palearctic-Afrotropical (spat)	1	0.1	1	1				

Table 2. Continued

Zoogeographical categories	Total number	Percentage	Vegetation belts					Alpine vegetation – over 2500 m
			Xerothermic oak forests – up to 600-700 m	Mesophyllic and xeromesophyllic oak-hornbeam forests – from 600-700 m to 900-1000 m	Beech forests - from 900-1000 to 1500-1600 m	Coniferous forests – from 1300-1600 m to 2000-2200 m	Subalpine vegetation – from 2000-2200 m to 2500 m	
Paleotropical-Mediterranean (ptm)	1	0.1	1					
Afrotropical-Mediterranean (atm)	1	0.1	1	1				
Oriental-Mediterranean (om)	1	0.1			1			
Species with Palaearctic distribution	580	78.4	202 (78.6)	283 (77.7)	305 (77.4)	192 (73.6)	50 (64.9)	7 (70.0)
PALAEARCTIC TYPE	196	26.5	98 (38.1)	113 (31.0)	116 (29.4)	67 (25.7)	20 (26.0)	1 (10.0)
Holopalaearctic (hop)	21	2.8	17	16	13	8	2	1
Transpalaearctic (tp)	58	7.8	30	38	41	22	6	
West and Central Palaearctic (wcp)	26	3.5	15	16	15	8	3	
West Palaearctic (wp)	25	3.4	18	15	15	11	5	
Disjunct Palaearctic (dp)	12	1.6	4	4	6	2	2	
South Palaearctic (sp)	2	0.3	1	1	1	1		
European-North African (ena)	17	2.3	2	9	7	5		
Euroiberian-Central Asian (esca)	10	1.3	6	6	4	1	1	
West Euroiberian-Central Asian (wesca)	1	0.1				1		
European-Central Asian (eca)	3	0.4		2	2	1		
East European-Central Asian (eeca)	1	0.1	1	1	1			
European-West Central Asian (ewca)	3	0.4	1	1	2	3	1	
European-Southwest Asian (eswa)	6	0.8	3	1	2	2		
European-Iran-Turanian (eit)	8	1.1		2	4	2		
European-Turanian (et)	3	0.4		1	3			
EUROSIBERIAN TYPE	328	44.3	74 (28.8)	148 (40.7)	171 (43.4)	115 (44.1)	29 (36.4)	6 (60.0)
Holoeuroiberian (hoes)	53	7.2	18	33	36	23	3	
West and Central Euroiberian (wces)	26	3.5	8	10	20	9	1	1
West Euroiberian (wes)	27	3.6	8	14	13	11	2	
Disjunct Euroiberian (des)	38	5.1	12	18	21	11	3	1
European and South Siberian (ess)	11	1.5	6	9	8	1	1	
European-Anatolian (ean)	4	0.5	1	3	2	1		

Table 2. Continued

Zoogeographical categories	Total number	Percentage	Vegetation belts					
			Xerothermic oak forests – up to 600-700 m	Mesophyllic and xeromesophyllic oak-hornbeam forests – from 600-700 m to 900-1000 m	Beech forests - from 900-1000 to 1500-1600 m	Coniferous forests – from 1300-1600 m to 2000-2200 m	Subalpine vegetation – from 2000-2200 m to 2500 m	Alpine vegetation – over 2500 m
European (e)	137	18.5	14	50	59	47	15	4
Central and South European-Anatolian (csean)	2	0.3		2	1			
Central and South European (cse)	24	3.2	6	7	8	9	3	
Central and Southeast European (csee)	6	0.8	1	2	3	3	1	
MEDITERRANEAN TYPE	43	5.7	29 (11.3)	21 (5.8)	11 (2.8)	4 (5.2)	1 (10.0)	
Mediterranean and South Siberian (mss)	1	0.1	1	1				
Mediterranean and Southwest Siberian (msws)	1	0.1	1					
Mediterranean-Central Asian (mca)	6	0.8	5	5	3	1	1	
Mediterranean-West Central Asian (mwca)	2	0.3		2				
Northeast Mediterranean-Iran-Turanian (nemit)	2	0.3	1		1			
Mediterranean-Turanian (mt)	2	0.3	2	1				
North Mediterranean-Turanian (nmt)	3	0.4	1	2				
South European and South Siberian (sess)	2	0.3	1	1	1			
Central and South European-Iran-Turanian (cseit)	1	0.1	1					
Central and Southeast European-Iran-Turanian (cseit)	1	0.1			1			
Central and South European-North African (csena)	1	0.1		1	1			
Holomediterranean (hom)	11	1.4	9	3	2	1		
North Mediterranean (nm)	4	0.5	4	3	2			
South European (se)	3	0.4	1			2		
East Mediterranean (em)	1	0.1		1				
Balkan-Anatolian (ban)	2	0.3	2	1				
ENDEMICS	14	1.9	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)	7 (1.8)	6 (2.3)	1 (1.3)	
Balkan subendemic (Ebs)	1	0.1				1		
Balkan endemic (Eb)	3	0.4		1	3			
Bulgarian endemic (Ebg)	8	1.1	1		3	4		
Regional endemic (Er)	2	0.3			1	1	1	
Total	742		257 (34.7)	364 (49.2)	394 (53.2)	261 (35.3)	78 (10.4)	10 (1.3)

resented). The number of taxa of these categories in the separate vegetation belts varies from 4% to 40.0% (1-59 species) and increases with height. Most Eurosiberian species are found in the beech and coniferous forest belts. In the sub-alpine and alpine belts the Eurosiberian species predominate over the other zoogeographical categories (36.4-60.0%). A number of disjunctive areas are presented – a longitudinal disjunction for parts of Siberia and Central Asia (Tables 2 and 3) and latitudinal disjunction with typical for the Eurosiberian complex boreomontane, boreoalpine and arctic-alpine distribution (GORODKOV, 1984; JOSIFOV, 1988). Of interest is the significant presence of Eurosiberian species in the two lower vegetation belts, which can be explained in 2 ways: 1) It is possible part of these species to have uncleared Palaearctic distribution; 2) It is supposed that the humid mountain valleys characterized with cooler climate, have facilitated the migration of the mentioned above forms to the lowlands. Finding of boreomontane forms at low altitudes has also been reported for other insect groups as Heteroptera and Cerambycidae (JOSIFOV, 1963, 1976; GEORGIEV & HUBENOV, 2006). For Cerambycide this fact is due to the large afforestations with conifers in the first vegetation belt. Probably because of this reason many boreomontane and montane species of the family, fed on conifers, go down below 600 m a.s.l.

The Mediterranean species (combined into 16 zoogeographical categories) are 43 (5.7%). They are presented mainly in the first 3 vegetation belts and their number rapidly decreases with the altitude. Because of the big variety of the areas, this group is divided into many subgroups with different origin, distribution and ecological peculiarities of the taxa. This complexity contributes to establishing of various zoogeographical classifications for Bulgaria (JOSIFOV, 1981, 1986, 1988, 1999; GRUEV 1988, 1995, 2000a, 2000b, 2000c, 2000d, 2002; HEISS & JOSIFOV, 1990, GRUEV & KUSMANOV 1994, HUBENOV 1996; POPOV, 2002). The Mediterranean species, established in one or two vegetation belts, prevail (Table 2). A significant percentage of these species and their relatively scarce populations are due to the lower ecological flexibility of the Mediterranean forms in comparison with the previous ones. The Mediterranean species include from 2.8% to 11.3% (1 to 29 species) of Diptera of the separate vegetation belts of Pirin Mt. (Table 3). The Holomediterranean (10 species – 1.3%) and Mediterranean-Central Asian (6 species – 0.8%) species are the most numerous. In the subalpine belt one Mediterranean species is established (*Lamproscatella*

unipunctata – Mediterranean-Central Asian species of the family Ephydriidae) and Mediterranean species have not been found in the alpine belt.

Endemics. This category includes taxa, which are not distributed outside the Balkan Peninsula. The percentage of endemism is low in Diptera (14 species – 1.9%). The Balkan and Bulgarian endemic forms prevail. The main part of the Pirin endemic species is related to the beech and coniferous belts (6-7 species, or 1.8-2.3%). This allows most of them to be accepted as postglacial neoendemics and to be connected with the Eurosiberian forms. Local endemics have not been established among Diptera of Pirin Mt. The Pirin dipterans are rare and mostly are newly described taxa (one Balkan endemic from 1862, 2 species from 1940 and 1942 and all others after 1970).

Conclusion

A total of 742 two-winged species that belong to 43 families have been reported from Pirin Mt. The dipterous fauna can be divided into 2 main groups: 1) species with Mediterranean type of distribution (48 species, or 6.4%) – more thermophilic and distributed mainly in the southern parts of the Palaearctic. Five species of southern type, distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it, can be formally related to this group as well; 2) species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (694 species, or 93.6%) – more cold-resistant and widely distributed in the Palaearctic. One hundred fifty-five species of northern type, distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it, can be formally related to this group as well. The zoogeographical character of the Tachinidae fauna is determined by the second group. The ration of the two groups is different in the separate vegetation belts of Pirin Mt. (Table 3).

Xerothermic oak forests (257 species, or 34.7%). From the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (32 species, or 12.5%) the Mediterranean-Central Asian, Holomediterranean and North Mediterranean species are most numerous and from the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (225 species, or 87.5%) the Holarctic and Transpalaearctic species are best represented.

Mesophyllic and xeromesophyllic mixed forests (364 species, or 49.2%). From the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (24 species, or 6.6%) the Mediterranean-Central Asian, Holomediterranean and North Mediterranean species prevail and from the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (340 spe-

cies, or 93.4%) – the Holarctic, Transpalearctic, Holoeurosiberian and European species are best represented. The number of the Holarctic-Oriental, Holarctic, Transpalearctic, Holoeurosiberian and European species is increased. The percentage of the Mediterranean species decreases.

Beech forests (394 species, or 53.2%). From the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (13 species, or 3.3%) the Mediterranean-Central Asian species are most numerous and from the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (381 species, or 96.7%) – the Holarctic, Transpalearctic, Holoeurosiberian and European species. The number of the Holarctic-Oriental, Palaearctic-Oriental, Holarctic, Transpalearctic, Holoeurosiberian, West and Central Eurosiberian, European and endemic species is increased. The percentage of the Mediterranean forms decreases.

Coniferous forests (261 species, or 35.3%). From the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (4 species, or 1.5%) only the Mediterranean-Central Asian, Holomediterranean and South

European species are presented and from the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (257 species, or 98.5%) the Holarctic, Transpalearctic, Holoeurosiberian and European species prevail. The distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it species of southern type have not been established. The number of the Cosmopolitan species is increased, the number of endemics is high and the Mediterranean forms greatly decrease.

Subalpine vegetation (78 species, or 10.4%). One species with Mediterranean type of distribution (Mediterranean-Central Asian) has been established. From the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (28 areographical categories) the Holarctic and European species are most numerous. This part of Pirin Mt. is poorly explored.

Alpine vegetation (10 species, or 1.3%). Only species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution of 7 areographical categories have been established. The European species are most numerous (4 species). Investigations of this part of Pirin Mt. almost lack.

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Двукрилите насекоми (Insecta: Diptera) на Пирин

Здравко ХУБЕНОВ

(Резюме)

На Пирин са установени 742 вида двукрили, които спадат към 43 семейства. Най-много видове са намерени в пояса на буковите гори (394 вида – 53.2%). Установените видове принадлежат към 72 ареалогрaфски категории. В зоогеографско отношение се очертават 2 основни групи: 1) видове с медитерански тип на разпространение (48 вида – 6.4%) – по-топлолюбиви и разпространени предимно в южните части на Палеарктика, към които формално са прибавени и 5 вида от южен тип, разпространени и извън Палеарктика; 2) видове с палеарктичен и евросибирски тип на разпространение (694 вида – 93.6%) – по-студенолюбиви и по-широко разпространени в Палеарктика, към които формално са отнесени и 155 вида от северен тип, разпространени и извън Палеарктика. Зоогеографският характер на тахинидната фауна се определя от втората група. Съотношението на двете групи е различно в отделните растителни пояси на Пирин.